

**EFFECTS OF BRAILLE AND TYPEWRITING SKILLS ON ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS WITH VISUAL
IMPAIRMENT IN SPECIAL EDUCATION SCHOOL TUDUN MALIKI, KANO
STATE.**

BY

**SAIFULLAHI MUKHTAR SADIQ
SPS/18/MSE/00030**

**SUPERVISOR:
PROFESSOR YA'U MUSA DANTATA**

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the product of my own research work; conducted, written and compiled by myself under the supervision of Prof. Ya'u Musa Dantata and has not been previously presented for any degree or certificate at any university or institution. All sources are duly acknowledged.

SaifullahiMukhtarSadiq
SPS/18/MSE/00030

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the research work has been read and approved for the award of the Master Degree in Special Education (Visual Impairment); and confirmed that this research work was carried out by Saifullahi Mukhtar Sadiq SPS/18MSE/00030 under my supervision.

Prof. Ya'u Musa Dantata
Supervisor

Date

Prof. Ya'u Musa Dantata
Head of Department

Date

APPROVAL PAGE

This dissertation has been read and approved as having satisfied the requirements for the award of Master degree in Special Education (Visual Impairment).

Prof. Abu Egwa Ozegya
External Examiner

Date

Dr. Abubakar Isa Ibrahim
Internal Examiner

Date

Prof. Ya'u Musa Dantata
Supervisor

Date

Prof. Ya'u Musa Dantata
Head of Department

Date

Dr. Musa H. Darma
Representative of the Board of the School
of Post Graduate Studies

Date

DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to my Parents: Alhaji Mukhtar Abubakar and Hajiya Rukayya Mukhtar for their moral, and financial support which helped me to realize my academic goals.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

IDEA:	Individual with Disabilities Education Act
VA:	Visual Acuity
NLP:	No Light Perception
NFB:	National Federation of Blind
UBECE:	Universal Basic Education Certificate Examination
SSCE:	Senior School Certificate Examination
WAEC:	West Africa Examination Council
NECO:	National Examination Council
BWST:	Braille Writing Skill Test
TST:	Typewriting Skill Test
NPE:	National Policy on Education

ABSTRACT

This study focused on the effect of Braille writing skills and typewriting skills on academic performance of primary pupils with visual impairment at Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State. The study adopted quasi-experimental design. The population of the study consisted of all the 53 pupils with visual impairment at special education school TudunMaliki, Kano state. The sample size for the study was 24 pupils with visual impairment drawn from primary 4,5,6 through purposive sampling technique. Five hypotheses were formulated based on the objectives of the study. Two instruments of data collection were used in this study. The instrument included: Braille Writing Skill Test (BWST) with reliability index of 0.82, and Typewriting Skill Test (TST) with reliability index of 0.79. Therefore, the data of the study were collected by the administration of test after 8 weeks of interventions on Braille writing skills and typewriting skills. The data related to the hypotheses of the study was analyzed using t-test. The findings of the study revealed that the effect of Braille writing skills was positive on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment when properly exposed to Braille skills (obtained t-value $6.53 > 1.71$ critical t-value). Likewise, the effect of typewriting skills was positive on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment when properly exposed to typewriter skills (obtained t-value $11.12 > 1.71$ critical t-value). Based on the findings of the study, recommendations were made among which include: Pupils with visual impairment should be motivated to constantly practice Braille Writing Skills in order to improve their academic performance. Pupils with visual impairment should be motivated to constantly practice typewriting skills in order to improve their academic performance.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Literacy for all children constitutes the cornerstone of education. In essence, the acquisition of literacy skills provides all the pre – requisite for Performance in areas of life, from school to employment (Koenig & Holbrook, 2000). Literacy is defined by Argyopoulos and Martos (2006) as the ability to read and write at such a level as to be able to meet daily living needs. The ability to read and write is the foundation of education. Research has shown that 80% of learning is by vision (Ozaji & Abosi, 1985). This means that pupils with visual impairment only have 20% to be compensated with other senses. Perhaps attempts to educate the children with visual impairment would have been a failure without the development of reading and writing. No wonder, different people at different times make different attempts to enable this category of people communicate with one another in writing (i.e. Braille). Notable of these attempts were those of Valentin Hauy, Charles Barbier and Louise Braille (Abang, 2005).

Invariably, the beginning of formal education for pupils with visual impairment could be traced to the founding of the first school for the blind in 1785 in Paris by Valentin Hauy. According to Maccuspie (2002) cited in Iroegbu (2010), Hauy believed that if he could teach children with visual impairment to read and write they will have an opportunity for employment and self sufficiency. Hauy's effort was complemented by Charles Barbier when he developed a system of raised dots comprising 12 – dots, this system was enthusiastically received by Louis Braille who was a student of the school for the blind Paris, Louise Braille modified it to 6 – dots, thus, providing the means of reading and writing for pupils with visual impairment.

Figure 1.2: Louis Braille's 6 Dots

Braille literacy remains the major and the most important medium of communication for those who are both totally and partially blind. Even in most cases those who can manage to read large print are almost non – existence in Nigerian Schools (Ozoji & Abozi, 1985).

The research of Willoughby and Duff (1989), Ryles (1996) and Schroeder (1997) showed that Braille is the path to literacy for pupils whose vision loss impedes their ability to read and write print. Experts in the field of education of pupils with visual impairment have recognized the importance of teaching Braille to children whose vision is not enough to read regular print comfortably and at a competitive rate for a sustained period of time. Braille is literacy building block and in turn, literacy is a building block for independent.

Pupils with visual impairment need literacy in Braille skills to attain their academic potentiality. A research conducted by Bidi (1997) showed that Braille skills provide available means for pupils with visual impairment to learn, hence literacy in Braille skills directly correlates to academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

Academic performance is the outcome of educational activity, the general and collective or holistic instructional outcomes which reflect the current level of a child's learning progress in school work or the level of schooling a child has completed (Annie, Howard, Stoker & Mildred, 2009). According to Haruna, Ayo and Gambo (2012) academic performance is commonly measured by using performance tests. Examples of performance tests are end of term or semester examinations and academic year examinations as well as certificate examinations like NECO, WAEC, etc. However, there

is no general agreement on how academic performance is best tested or which aspects are most important to test (Yeung, 2013).

According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016) the skills of touch typing (typewriting skill) is now recognized as an essential skill that pupils with visual impairment must acquire if they have to survive in today's knowledge economy. The reasons are very compelling; not everyone can read and write Braille, in inclusive settings children with visual impairment must type and submit their assignments and exams in full to the examiners. Skills of touch (typewriting skill) are taught to pupils with visual impairment from middle basic level in special education schools in Nigeria. Writing is an important aspect in the context of education. Education is generally understood to encompass literacy, which is defined as the ability to read and write; for pupils with visual impairment, typewriting skill become survival skills in an academic life (Sykes & Ozoji, 1992).

According to the National Policy on Education (NPE) (2013), all necessary facilities that would ensure easy access to education shall be provided and special education training such as Braille reading and writing as well as typewriting skills for pupils with visual impairment should be taught at primary school stage. Globally, Braille writing skill and typewriting skill were and still are the primary medium of writing among learners with visual impairment (Lowenfield, 1991). Braille writing is a system of writing in which the embossed sign of each character is formed by combination of six raised dots appearing on Braille paper (Ozoji, 2005). While, typewriting is a system of writing in which manual or electronic machine with keyboard is used for writing directly onto a sheet of paper (Rundell, 2004). Both Braille literacy skill and typewriting skill remain the major and the most instrumental factors in academic performance of children with visual

impairment. Braille literacy and typewriting skills affect academic performance of children with visual impairment either positively or negatively.

According to Spungin (1996), academic performance of children with visual impairment is mostly relied on Braille literacy skills; it is one of the strong determinant factors of educational performance of pupils with visual impairment. Similarly, the skill of touch typing (typewriting skill) is one of the extra – curriculum contents necessary for pupils with visual impairment (Sykes & Ozoji, 1992). Therefore, the Braille literacy and typewriting skills are described as additional curriculum contents (unique/expanded core curriculum) which pupils with visual impairment ought to be taught in order to perform excellently in the school and function as literate members of the society (Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016). Since the Braille literacy and typewriting skill become the part of curriculum contents of children with visual impairment in school and are commonly measured and evaluated by using performance tests such as teacher – made – test and end of term examinations. These may reflect the academic performance of children with visual impairment either good or bad, high or low. Hence, Lowenfeld (1991) cited in Ochigbo (2008) explained that among pupils with visual impairment, those who have Braille literacy and typewriting skills tend to have good and high academic performance.

Based on gender, the importance of learning Braille skills and typewriting skills to both male and female pupils with visual impairment cannot be underestimated. According to the Daniela (2005), the importance of learning Braille skills and typewriting skills by male pupils with visual impairment is equally important to female pupils with visual impairment. For both male and female pupils with visual impairment, learning Braille skills and typewriting skills is the key to literacy and academic performance. Similarly, it is essential for both male and female pupils with visual impairment to learn Braille skills

and typewriting skills in the same manner. However, both the males and the females learn the skills in many different ways, depending upon their inborn abilities, their experiences, and their motivation and interests. For that reason, every teacher should have knowledge of methods that are gender-responsive for teaching male and female pupils with visual impairment (Mousty & Beterlson, 2001). Teaching Braille skills and typewriting skills to both male and female pupils with visual impairment is more than just teaching them the meaning of the Braille symbols or typewriter usage. Male pupils with visual impairment learn to write using Braille and typewriter just as female pupils with visual impairment learn to write using Braille and typewriter. Both the males and the females with visual impairment must learn the meanings of symbolic representations (Braille characters) and how those representations form words, sentences, paragraphs etc which when put together communicate a unique message. Also, both male and female pupils with visual impairment must learn the typewriting skills in order to write their assignments and examinations to the sighted teachers. Therefore, many teaching methods which work for male pupils with visual impairment can also work for female pupils with visual impairments, possibly with some modifications (Koenig & Holbrook, 2000). Furthermore, according to Agyropoulos and Martos (2008), gender is not a factor which determines the difference in Braille skills and typewriting skills between male and female pupils with visual impairment. Also, gender is not a determinant factor of difference on academic performance among male and female pupils with visual impairment.

A comparative study was conducted by Ochigbo (2008) to find out whether or not, there is relationship between skill in Braille writing and typewriting. The researcher, hypothesized that “There is no significant relationship between skill in Braille writing and skill in typewriting among children with visual impairment.” The calculated value ($r = 0.43$) obtained by the researcher was compared to the critical value of ‘ r ’ 0.65. hence, the

obtained value ($r = 0.43$) is less than the critical value (0.65) and that is an indication of low level negative correlation between skill of Braille writing and skill in typewriting among children with visual impairment. Thus, the researcher upheld the null hypothesis, meaning that there was no statistically significant relationship between the skill in Braille writing and the skill in typewriting among children with visual impairment.

Another comparative study by Birch (2001) between the Braille writing skill and skill of touch typing on academic performance of children with visual impairment indicated that there was significant difference between the mean scores of both Braille writing and the skill of touch typing skills of children with visual impairment ($t = 2.84$). The calculated t – value (2.84) was greater than the critical value of ‘ t ’ (2.145) at 0.05 level of significance. This means that the difference between the Braille writing and the touch typing skills was statistically significant and as a result the researcher rejects the null hypothesis in support of alternative hypothesis.

A study on effect of Braille skill on learning English language among pupils with visual impairment was conducted by Mitiku (2020). One of the null hypotheses of the study was stated that, there is no significant gender difference in Braille skill means scores of pupils with visual impairment. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The finding revealed that the obtained t -value 1.16 was less than the critical t -value 2.13. Thus, the null hypothesis, was retained, meaning that there was no statistically significant difference in Braille skill means scores between male and female pupils with visual impairment.

Therefore, it is based on these background that the present study explores the “effects of Braille and typewriting skills on academic performance of primary school pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School Tundun Maliki, Kano state.”

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Literacy plays a key role in an educational programme for pupils with visual impairment just as it does in the academic life of children who are sighted. Also, Braille literacy skill as well as skill of touch typing (typewriting skill) is equally significant for children with visual impairment to participate actively in teaching and learning process.

It is the fact that both Braille writing skill and typewriting skill are being taught to children with visual impairment right from elementary stage. This enables children with visual impairment to acquire writing skill as one of the aspect of literacy so as to compete with their counterpart who are sighted.

Despite the enormous significance of Braille literacy and typewriting skills to pupils with visual impairment at Special Education School Tudun Maliki Kano State, it has been observed that pupils with visual impairment find it difficult to write in Braille and use typewriting in writing proficiently. This constitutes the major impediment to their academic performance. Personal experience and contacts with pupils with visual impairment by the researcher have showed that poor academic performance of pupils with visual impairment is often traced to the problem of low level of Braille literacy and typewriting skills. It has been observed also that the level of typewriting skill among children with visual impairment is lower in comparison to Braille literacy skill. This sometimes affect negatively the academic performance of pupils with visual impairment right from elementary level to higher level of education, since not every teacher can read Braille, pupils with visual impairment must write their assignments and examinations by using typewriting.

Therefore, this problem prompted the researcher to undertake a study on “effects of Braille and typewriting skills on academic performance of primary school pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School Tundun Maliki, Kano state.”

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Examine the effect of Braille writing skill on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.
2. Determine the effect of typewriting skill on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.
3. Establish the difference between Braille writing and typewriting skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.
4. Find out whether or not there is gender difference in Braille writing skill on academic performance of children with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.
5. Find out whether or not there is gender difference in typewriting skill on academic performance of children with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.

1.4 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant mean effect of Braille writing skill on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment.
2. There is no significant mean effect of typewriting skill on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment.
3. There is no significant mean difference between Braille and typewriting skills on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment.
4. There is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skill means scores of pupils with visual impairment.

5. There is no significant gender difference in typewriting skill mean scores of pupils with visual impairment.

1.5 Significance of the Study

It is hoped that the findings of this study will be useful to teachers of pupils with visual impairment, school administrators, and parent of pupils with visual impairment and ministry of education. It is hoped that this study will be beneficial to teachers of children with visual impairment in the sense that the teacher will acquire instructional skills of teaching Braille literacy and typewriting skills for children with visual impairment.

It is expected that the findings of the study will be beneficial to school administrators as they will understand the importance of Braille literacy and typewriting skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment performance of children visual impairment so that qualified teachers with knowledge and skills of Braille literary and typewriting skill should be assigned to teach Braille and typewriting skills to children with visual impairment.

It is hoped that the findings of the study will be beneficial to parent of children with visual impairment in the sense that the parents will understand that Braille literacy and typewriting skills affected the academic performance and Performance of their children with visual impairment either positively or negatively, hence the parent will be motivated to provide newly modernized learning materials such as Braille machines and typewriters for their children with visual impairment.

The study will be beneficial to ministry of education as it will provide the ministry of education as it will provide the ministry of education with information on the needs to update the Braille curriculum and re-design typewriting skill content for children with visual impairment.

Finally, the study will be useful to other researchers who may want to undertake similar studies in areas such as Braille literacy skills, typewriting skills and children with visual impairment.

1.6 Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study covered Special Education School TudunMaliki, Kano State. But, the study was only limited to primary school section. Also, the study delimited to primary 4, 5 and 6 pupils with visual impairment. Likewise, the study scoped on Braille writing skills, typewriting skills and academic performance of pupils with visual impairment.

1.7 Operational Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined for the purpose of ordinary readers:

Braille: It is a system of writing by using 6 dots and reading tactually.

Braille Literacy Skill: it is the ability of pupils with visual impairment to read and write Braille proficiently.

Typewriting Skill: it is proficiency and mastery in typewriting by pupils with visual impairment.

Academic Performance: It is knowledge attained or skills developed in school subject by test scores.

Visual Impairment: This refers to a defect or malformation of the visual organ (eye).

Pupils with Visual Impairment: refers to those groups of pupils whose visions are abnormal due to disease, accident or malformation to the extent that they need special education programmed or intervention in order to succeed academically.

Gender: This denotes either male or female pupil with visual impairment.

CHAPTER TWO REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviewed some literatures that are related to this study. Write up of various scholars were extensively reviewed. Thus, this chapter contained the following areas: conceptual background, concept of visual impairment, concept of Braille, concept of typewriting, academic performance of pupils with visual impairment, theoretical framework, empirical studies, summary ad uniqueness of the study.

2.2 Conceptual Background

2.2.1 Concept of Visual Impairment

Impairment, according to Ozoji (2005), is a defect, a deviation, a disturbance of the organs of the body. This can be in the structure or in the functioning of the organs. Abang (2005) described impairment as any deviation from normal, which results in defective function, structure development of any part of the body include organs of the body such as eyes, ears, nose, brain, throat and so on.

Visual impairment is an umbrella term that accommodates all types and degree of visual loss or deviation (Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016). Visual impairment is a condition which refers to a dysfunction or defect of the organ that deals with the sense of sight (Okeke, 2001). Kolo (1984) opined that visual impairment is a generic term describes eye defects of both partial and total blindness. Also, Individual with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) (1997) defined visual impairment as “impairment in vision that even with correction adversely affects a child’s educational performance”. In their opinion, visual problem that limits a child’s educational performance is visual impairment.

In their view of Jatau, Uzo and Lere (2010), stated that there is no single definition of the visual impairment and that experts in the field however, have maintained that there are three general ways in which the definition of visual impairment can be approached

namely: medically (legally), occupationally and educationally. Medically, a child is said to have visual impairment if he/she has a “central visual acuity of 20/200VA (vision activity) or less in the better eye with best corrections or a diameter of visual field that does not subtend an angle greater than 20 degrees (Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

The medical definition relies on and is interpreted from tests such as a Snellen Chart Test commonly conducted in hospitals and clinics when a child has problem with seeing well. The chart comprises alphabets of varying boldness or sizes that a child is expected to read from a distance of 20 feet (standard distance from the chart). This is the upper value of the pseudo ‘fraction’. It is called pseudo because the fraction does not have arithmetic property of cancellation to arrive at an answer. The lower value of the fraction represents the smallest size line of letters on the chart that the child is able to read from the 20ft distance. If the child is only able to read the 20ft line of letters, it means he/she could not read lesser line of letters such as at 100ft, 70ft, etc. the result is interpreted to mean that what another child with normal vision can see at 200ft away, the child being tested and who has the result of 20/200 Visual Acuity (VA) can see the same letters only when he/she is brought to 20ft distance. This part of the medical definition concentrates on a child’s central visual acuity (Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

The second part of the definition makes use of visual field i.e the range the child can see from the central to the peripheral (sides) without turning the head. This range is 180° for a child with normal vision. If a child’s visual field is restricted by disease or injury to 5° to 10° , the child according to Sykes and Ozaji (1992), is said to have visual impairment related to field of vision. The child has what is called ‘tunnel’ vision which means he can only see objects in the centre but not from the sides. If he must see objects from one side, he must turn his head to that side. This condition constitutes a severe limitation in social environment. The child has to turn his head to both sides of the central

vision to be able to know what is happening on the periphery of his vision (Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

The occupational definition of visual impairment has its origin from British. It is defined as a child whose vision is so much impaired that he cannot see and perform the duties that involves the use of the eyes. This definition has been criticized because of the emphasis and limitation it places on visually impaired person's ability to function well only in the discharge of his work leaving other activities that are vital for his existence as a child (Ozaji, 2001).

The educational definition of visual impairment explains that a child with visual problems include the blind whose vision is limited (either through visual acuity, visual field, colour or form of discrimination) to such an extent that the person may require educational modification and adaptations in order to benefit from learning activities that involves the use of sight (Jatau, Uzo & Lere, 2001). According to Ozajil, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016). Educationally, a child is said to have visual impairment (blindness) if he cannot read print even when enlarged. Such a child can only read by means of touch (Braille) and audio (recorded material) modes. This definition is teacher friendly and can quickly be used to confirm cases of visual impairment from other sources such as the medical professional or to refer the child for further medical attention. In the view of Abang (2005) educational definition of visual impairment considers the extent to which a child's vision affects his learning and makes special methods and materials necessary.

According to Abang (2005), in the United States of America, the terms partially sighted, low vision, legally blind or totally blind are used by schools, colleges and educational institutions to describe children's visual impairments. Therefore, visual impairment is a range of vision loss from mild to severe which include the following three major features:

a. Partial Sightedness

It is a term used to refer children with poor sight but whose sight is not as poor as to be regarded as blind. The partially sighted, according to British Educational Act (1994) cited in Abang (2005), are “pupils who by reasons of defective vision cannot follow the ordinary curriculum without detriment to the sight or to their educational development but can be educated by specific methods involving the use of sight”, they carryout their daily activities by using their remaining vision to the fullest. Many of them suffer either myopia (short sightedness), hypermetropia (long sightedness) or astigmatism (blurred vision).

b. Low Vision

According to Okeke (2001), low vision is a concept that is recent in the history of visual impairment. In the past children with visual impairment are referred to the blind and the partially sighted. With the Barrage’s findings in 1986, low vision have been included under the visual impairment. Barrage (1986) described children with low vision as those who might have been certified blind but have some residual vision. Barrage considers children are having low vision when they have limitation in distance vision but are able to see objects and materials when they are within a few inches or at a maximum of two feet away (Dantata & Diso, 2013).

c. Blindness

According to Barrage (1986) cited in Dantata and Diso (2013), a child is considered blind when he/she have only light perception or have no vision and must learn through Braille and related media without the use of vision. Children with blindness according to the degree of vision loss have no light perception; they use touch (tactile) and auditory (hearing) to carry out what their sighted peers do in class and out of class

environments (Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016). Total blindness is the complete lack of vision and visual light perception and is clinically recorded as No light perception (NLP).

2.2.2 Characteristics of Children with Visual Impairment

A child with visual impairment can be identified through many of the characteristics or behavior indications which they usually exhibits. The visual defects of many pupils can easily be identified before enrollment in school (Dantata & Diso, 2013). There are, however, some pupils whose visual impairment has gone undetected for many years. Some may be detected only in their senior primary level as a result of their extensive use of their eyes in reading and other academic work. This delay may be attributed to gross inadequacy of vision screening procedures and instruments during the pupils early primary school years, the few available ones may carelessly handle the exercise due to the paucity of those trained to do this work (Dantata & Diso, 2013). According to Dantata and Diso (2013), the following observable signs are the vital areas of focus to all regular school teachers in their efforts to identify children who have one visual problem or the other:

1. **Eye Discomfort:** Pupils who complain of burning, itching, or scratchiness of the eyes may be experiencing a vision problem. The eyes may be reddish in colour most of the time and may have frequently pus on the eyes. The child may also complain of double or blurred vision, pains, aches and frequent rubbing of the eyes, headaches, dizziness, nausea or vomiting.
2. **Poor Eye Hand Coordination:** pupils having visual problems usually exhibits poor eye hand coordination. The accuracy that is supposed to exist between what the eyes are seeing and what the hands are to catch may not be there.
3. **Poor Spacing in Writing:** A pupil who has problems of spacing his/her words when writing should be suspected of having a visual problem.

4. Unusual facial serious visual problems demonstrate on unusual amount of squinting, frowning or facial distortion while reading or performing tasks that require either close or distant observation.
5. Shuts or Covers One Eye When Performing a Task: pupils who are having difficulties with eyes may close one eye, thrust their head either forward or backwards, expression which shows that they are not focusing well.
6. Confuse And Reverse Letters: A pupil who gets confuse and reverse letters if similar shapes e.g.pq and g. b and d, n and m, etc may be encountering some difficulties with his vision such as child often skips letters, words or tines while reading.
7. Disparity in Performance: A possible indication of a visual loss is the observation that there is a disparity between the expected and actual Performance of the pupils suspected of having the visual problems. The pupils concerned appropriate for children of approximately the same age, grade or intelligence.
8. Difficulties in Completing Long Reading Assignment in Time: A child has difficulties in completing long reading assignment or other school tasks involving extensive used of eyes but experience little difficulty in oral spoken direction has a visual problems.
9. Holding A Reading Materials At An Inappropriate Distance: such pupils are comfortable with task that are brought too close or too far or frequently changing the distance from near to far or from far to near because of the inability of the eyes to focus well on the reading tasks or objects.
10. Difficulty in Seeing Distance Objects: pupils who have difficulties in setting distant objects have the tendency to avoid reading and copying from the

chalkboard or textbooks. Such pupils prefer that the materials be read for them because they understand better (Dantata and Diso, 2013).

2.2.3 Classification of Children with Visual Impairment

According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), there are three paradigms by which children with visual impairment are classified. These are:

1. Age at onset of vision loss
2. Degree of vision loss
3. Type of residual vision

1. **Age at Onset of Vision Loss:** This means the period at which the impairment occurred. The time of vision loss in the life of a child can be used to classify the children with visual impairment. If it occurs before or at birth or during infancy (below two years) the child is classified as having congenital visual loss. However, the child is classified as having adventitious visual loss if the impairment occurs after two years. Visual memory is an important factor in learning for it can influence one's development of concepts and other aspects important to learning. In teaching children with visual impairment, it is important to find out the age at which vision loss occurred because it helps the teacher to know whether the child has visual memory of concepts including colours in the environment or not. This knowledge is instructive in guiding the teacher about reference to concepts and colours (Sykes & Ozoji, 1992).

2. **Degree of visual Loss:** This can be used to classify the pupils into low vision and blindness. A child with low vision uses vision to learn, but according to Smith (2007), his/her visual disabilities interfere with daily functioning. Sykes and Ozoji (1992) used low vision to "describe those children with moderate, severe or profound levels of visual impairment but who have sufficient residual (remaining)

vision to function primarily in a sighted way”. Previously, such children, according to Sykes and Ozoji (1992), were labeled “partially sighted” or “legally blind”. Children with blindness according to the degree of vision loss have no light perception; they use touch (tactile) and auditory (hearing) to carry out what their sighted peers do in class and out of class environment. Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), stated that research shows that approximately 90% of children with visual impairment have low vision, that just about 10% have no light perception (blindness).

3. Type of residual vision: The eye is very sensitive. Any injury of the eye can result to serious consequences including limitation to see and to perform certain tasks. Children with visual impairment can be classified by the part of the eye that is affected. Thus, Myopia (near sightedness), hyperopia (far sightedness), glaucoma (restricted fluid in the eye), atrophy (reduced functioning of the optic nerve) etc are some vision disorders by which children with visual impairment can be classified. Some of these conditions can result to blindness and others to severe visual disabilities. Many of the disorders are correctible by lenses or surgery as in the case of cataract (Opacity of the lenses) (Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

2.2.4 Causes of Visual Impairment

There are many causes that may lead to loss of vision or visual impairment. Sykes and Ozoji (1992), Abang (2005), Dantata and Diso (2013) identified the following as the main and common causes of vision loss or visual impairment:

1. Diseases/infections of the Eye: This is one of the most common visual impairment. Bacterial infections such as Staphylococci aureus, neisseria, gonorrhoea, ophthalmia neonatorum, syphilis, etc are responsible for eye infection leading to visual impairments. Also, childhood diseases like measles and small pox virus which are not

well treated could leads to visual impairment. Others are Chlamydia, a micro organism which affects the conjunctiva, a lining of the eye and cornea causes a disease called Trachoma. Onchocerciasis (River blindness) is another causes of visual impairment.

2. **Hereditary:** Inherited conditions of visual impairment and retinitis pigmentosa are the most common causes of inherited visual loss. According to Jatau, Uzo and Lere (2001), if visually impaired persons marry the same status. There is high tendency for two couples that are visually impaired to give birth to a child of the same problem.
3. **Glaucoma:** This condition results due to raised pressure inside the eyes. The increased pressure impairs vision by damaging the optic nerve. Glaucoma is mostly seen in older adults and in some babies as well as those who are born with condition. According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), Glaucoma is caused when the fluid (aqueous humour) in the eye cannot drain properly which may ultimately lead to damage of the optic nerve. It develops painlessly but progressively. Children with glaucoma may complain of blurred vision, poor side vision and later there is considerable eye and head pain.
4. **Trachoma:** This occurs when a very contagious micro organism called Chlamydia trachomatis causes inflammation in the eye which may also damage eye sight. It is often found in the developing and under developed countries with poor water and sanitation facilities. According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), trachoma is a type of conjunctivitis caused by a highly contagious agent which is partly bacterial and partly viral which spread rapidly in poverty stricken and over crowded areas and where good hygiene and water are mostly lacking. The first symptoms of trachoma include eyes that water, burn or itch. The process of infection takes time that gradually leads to visual impairment if not promptly treated.

5. **Cataract:** This is cloudy area in part or the entire lens of the eye. In children without cataracts, the lens is crystal clear and allows light to pass through and focus on the retina. Cataracts prevent light from easily passing through the lens, and this causes loss of vision. Cataracts often form slowly and usually affect elderly. Symptoms include double vision, cloudy or blurry vision, difficulty seeing in dimly lit area, and bright lights, colours appear faded, etc. According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), cataract refers to cloudiness or opacity of the eye. Once the eye loses its transparency, vision is lost until the lens covering the eye is removed through eye surgery.
6. **Retinopathy:** This is a damage done to the small blood vessels which are responsible for nourishing the retina with blood and minerals. This occurs as a result of the inadequacy of insulin production caused by diabetes. Diabetes develops retinopathy which is one of the circulatory problems associated with general disease, diabetes. When the blood vessels that supply the retina become damaged, they shut down completely and the retina becomes inefficient which in turn affects and damages the optic nerves transmitting impulse to the brain. Retinopathy leads to a gradual loss of vision and then blindness which is irreversible.
7. **Age related macular degeneration:** This is a gradual and progressive deterioration of the macula, the most sensitive region of the retina. The condition leads to progressive loss of central vision (the ability to see fine details directly in front). Macular degeneration is often age related (it occurs in older persons), but sometime it can occur in young persons. Excessive exposure to sunlight and smoking can increase the risk for age related macular degeneration. Symptoms may include increased difficulty reading or watching TV, or distorted vision in which straight lines appear wavy or objects look large or smaller than normal.

8. **Malnutrition:** Visual impairment resulting from malnutrition usually occurs when there is a deficiency of vitamin A. This leads to dryness of the eyes called exophthalmia or xerophthalmia. Softness and ulceration of the cornea (Kerationalacia) follow it. All these lead to a neurological problem that causes visual impairment.
9. **Accidents and Injuries:**According to Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016), “various forms of injuries (home, vehicular, industrial) affecting the eye directly or indirectly often result to visual loss”. Injury to the eye while playing or at work or due to accidents may result in vision loss and impairment, particularly injuries to the cornea.

2.2.5 Refractive Errors in Children with Visual Impairment

Refractive errors also known as optical errors are types of vision problems or disorders which some children are experiencing. “Refractive errors caused by irregularities in the shape or size of the eyeball, cornea or the lens (Dantata and Diso, 2013)”. Refractive errors happen when the shape of a child’s eye keeps light from focusing correctly on child’s retina (a light sensitive layer of tissue in the back of the child’s eye). It also said that, the shape of the child’s eye does not bend light correctly, resulting in blurred image. Hence, refractive errors are vision problems that make it hard to see clearly. The main types of refractive errors outlined by Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016) are as follows:

1. Myopia (near – sightedness)
2. Hyperopia (far –sightedness)
3. Presbyopia (loss of near vision with age)
4. Astigmatism (blurred vision)
5. Strabismus (squint, crossed eye or wounding eyes)
 - i. Myopia (short sightedness): This is a refractive error which is due to the abnormal length of eyeball, as a result of light rays focus on a point in front of the retina. That is, the length of the eye or the shape of the cornea causes parallel

light rays to focus in front of the retina. A child with myopia see near objects more clearly than those at a distance. This type of problem (myopia) is on the increase, the only way for a child with this problem is to be referred to an eye center or hospital for optical treatment. The condition is correctible with spectacles/glasses containing concave glass (optical lenses).

- ii. **Hyperopia (Long Sightedness):**This is very simple error of the development of the eyeball. The eye ball instead of being spherical is oval in shape, light rays therefore focus behind the retina instead of focusing on it. That is, parallel light rays focus behind the retina, thus the child sees distant objects more clearly than near ones. The condition is correctible with spectacles/glasses containing convex spherical lenses.
- iii. **Astigmatism (blurred vision):** This is a result of an irregularity in the curvature of the cornea or lens of the eye. The rays of the light are refracted unevenly so that horizontal and vertical rays are focused at different points on the retina. The normal cornea is shaped like a perfect hemisphere with the same degree of slope on each plane. This makes the rays of light come together to meet at a single point on their journey to the retina. In the astigmatic eye, one corneal plane is steeper than the other, hence the rays of light fails to come together at the same point. As a result, two separate images are focused at two separate point along the visual axis. One point could be on the retina and the other in the front or one point could be on the retina and the other behind it or they could be both in front or behind it. The type of astigmatism is named of the location of the points of focus. These are as follows: short sighted astigmatism, long sighted astigmatism, or mixed astigmatism (Dantata & Diso, 2013).

Furthermore, Ozoji, Unachukwu and Kolo (2016) explained further that, the problem associated with astigmatism is that light rays fall in and around the retina rather than on the retina itself. Some fall in front, some behind and some on the retina. The cause of this condition is the unevenly shaped cornea where the curvature is not perfectly spherical. Astigmatism can be corrected with spectacles or glasses containing cylindrical lenses that diverge only the before or after the retina rays and directing them fall on the retina.

- iv. **Presbyopia:** According to Dantata and Diso (2013), presbyopia is derived from the Greek word meaning, “sight of age”. It is a condition in which the lens of the eye loses its ability to accommodate near objects. It is the only one of the four optical errors that we are all certain to acquire at some point in our lives, presbyopia is part of the natural process of ageing. It is the loss of the ability to use the near focusing muscles. In addition to blurring and difficulty with reading at normal distances, person with presbyopia will usually experience “tired eyes” or headaches while doing close work. Most people at the age of 40 or there about develop some degree of presbyopia and need glasses for close work.
- v. **Strabismus:** This is a condition affecting one or both eyes. This condition is often caused by an imbalance of the eye muscles which do not permit both eyes to simultaneously focus on the same object. The earlier strabismus is detected the easier it is to be corrected by a variety of ways spectacles, eye drops and surgery (Ozoji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

2.3 Concept of Braille

Braille literacy refers to the ability of pupils with visual impairment to write by using 6 dots and read tactually using the tip of the fingers (Koeing, 1992). According to Ozoji (2005), Braille as a system of reading and writing for pupils with visual impairment;

it is named after its inventor Louis Braille (1809 – 1852), a citizen of France. The embossed signs appear on a special paper (Braille sheet) as raised dots. A careful arrangement of these dots does give a Braille version of anything in print. Braille can be adapted to various usages e.g foreign and Nigerian languages of English, French, German, Igbo, Yoruba, Hausa, Music, Maths, etc. Braille is written either by hand with a stylus on a paper in a frame or by Braille machine and it is read tactually by fingers.

Braille reading and writing involves the conventional process of reading and writing like the sighted children. Before a child or an individual (sighted) could read and write in any language such a child or an individual must have been exposed to; and or must have mastered the letters of the alphabet in such language. Bu this knowledge, the child or individual must first foremost be exposed to letters of the alphabet of any language. Braille as a conventional system of reading and writing for children with visual impairment is a language of its own; and has its own letters of alphabet (i.e the basis of knowledge, and of any language). The mastery of these letters of the alphabet (simple known as the Braille alphabets) provides a leeway for any child or individual with visual impairment to read and write Braille (Ochigbo, 2016).

The sixty three (63) different Braille characters are formed by arranging the 6 dots in different positions and combinations. The first ten (10) letters of the alphabet (A-J) are formed by using dot 1 or dot 4 or both. Adding dot 3 to the first ten (10) letters of the alphabet forms the next ten (10) letters (K – T). while the last alphabet (u – z) are formed by the addition of the button left and right lower dots. However, it should be noted the letter “W” as initially omitted in the alphabetical arrangement because the French language (in which Braille originated) has no “W”, but was later adopted by the English – speaking countries. Also, punctuation marks, capital, account, mathematical, italic, termination, ditto and other signs exist in Braille as in print (Iroegbu, 2010).

2.3.1 Braille Writing Devices

There are varieties of Braille writing materials which children with visual impairment use. Some are low tech and cheaper while others are high – tech and expensive (Ochigbo, 2016).

- a.** Slate and stylus: The cheapest devices in Braille writing are slate and stylus. They are the oldest tools used by children with visual impairment to write text that they can read without assistance. Slate is made up of two pieces of plastic held together by a hinge at one end. The slate opens up to hold paper. The top part has rows of openings that are the same shape and size as a Braille cell. The back part has rows of indentations in the same size and shape of Braille cell. The stylus has two parts, the handle and a metal pin. The handle, which is available in a variety of shapes, is made up of wood, plastic or metal. The metal pin has pointed or rounded tip to form dots on the paper. The stylus is used to punch or emboss the Braille dots onto the paper held in the slate. The indentations in the slate prevent the stylus from punching a hole in the paper when the dots are embossed. Slates and stylus come in many shapes and size (Ochigbo, 2016).

According to Bishop (1988), cited in Ochigbo (2016) the slate frame has some holes known as “cell”. Six dots are located in each cell. Brailing with slate and stylus involves briefly the following procedures:

1. The slate is opened towards the left to fix Braille paper
2. The Braille paper is placed between the opened slate
3. Slate is thereafter close
4. The edges of the slate are pressed to ensure the paper is properly fitted
5. In the process of brailing, the stylus is held and used in punching the Braille paper fixed in between the slate through the hollows of the Braille cells

6. The writing is accomplished from right to left of the slate
 7. After writing the slate is opened again and the paper is removed
 8. The paper is turned over and read from left to right.
- b.** Perkins Braille: This is the most efficient device for producing Braille ‘by hand’ (i.e not generated by computer). The Perkin Braille is a mechanical writer which has nine keys. Six of which are used for embossing, each key corresponding to a dot in the Braille cell. When the six keys (three on either side of the space bar) are pressed down in the appropriate combination, raised letters and signs are embossed onto a sheet of manila paper, which is fed manually into the machine. Apart from the spacebar, which is positioned in the middle of the six embossing keys, two additional keys are used. The line spacing key, which is found on the extreme left of the embossing keys, and the backspace key, which is to the extreme right of the embossing keys (Aranyanak, 2014).

The Perkins Braille embossed dots on one side of the paper. However, unlike the slate and stylus which embossed dots on the underside of the paper, the Perkins Braille embosses dots upwards so that the user can read what he/she has written without having to remove the paper from the machine. To load paper, the following instructions are followed:

1. Turn the paper knob (on either side of the Perkins Braille) as far as it go, turning it counter clockwise
2. Open the print head by pushing the left most lever (on top of the Perkins Braille) all the way forward,
3. Insert the paper until it stops
4. Close the left most lever
5. Press the paper advanced key once to set the paper

6. Then brailing, dots are made by pressing one or more embossing keys simultaneously

To remove the paper, simply push the left most lever forward and remove the paper (Arif, 2013).

c. Electronic Braille embosser: It is connected to computer to generate and render text as tactile Braille cell for children with visual impairment. It press dots down onto a piece of paper to let the children with visual impairment read by using their fingers. Electronic Braille embosser is also known as Braille printers, it is similar to a laser or inkjet printer, but it works by embossing raised dots onto a specialized heavy weight paper rather than using ink or toner. However, to produce hardcopy Braille from electronic Braille embosser, it has to be connected to a computer and Braille translation software must be installed to translate text into Braille code, which is then typically printed on heavy weight paper (Arif, 2013).

2.3.2 Mechanics of Reading Braille

This refers to the movements made by the fingers during Braille reading, pupils with visual impairment must be taught those skills, because unlike the eyes, fingers had not been stimulated by the different environmental challenges (Kimeto, 2010). Teaching letter or symbol identification in Braille reading could not be separated from teaching correct finger and hand use. At the same time the child is learning the sounds and names of the letters, contractions and short form words, it is important to incorporate a programme to develop tactile perception in addition to proper reading mechanic. Although, many of the activities that are used with sighted and visually impaired pupils must have direct tactile contact with the symbol (Kimeto, 2010).

Moreover, since Braille could not be perceived without movement of the fingers over the Braille symbols, teaching children with visual impairment the correct way to

move their hands in order to locate and identify the symbols is a critical element of teaching the beginning of Braille reading. Pupils with visual impairment use different types of hand movement patterns in reading Braille. In general, the most efficient pattern is moving the two hands like scissors the left hand reads to the middle of the line, then the right hand takes over and begins to read independently to the right. The hands meet in the middle of the line of Braille and then separate. Pupils gradually learn to use their hands independently. Initially, they might locate the beginning of the line with the left hand and read with both hands until they approach the end of the line, when the left hand finds the next line. This technique requires both hands to have fairly equal perceptual ability (Kimeto, 2010).

In addition to using their hands independently, the faster Braille readers maintain contact with the Braille characters (whether the characters include dots in the upper or lower part of the cell or both). In the development of hand movement patterns in reading, the perception of Braille characters is the most important aspect of Braille reading. Therefore, the development of tactile perception and Braille letter recognition is needed for proper Braille reading. There is need to incorporate proper hand movement and a light finger touch with improving the ability to recognize and discriminate among Braille characters with both hands (Kimeto, 2010). Beginning pupils initially tend to stop and move their fingers up and down on a character in an attempt to identify it. The practice, known as scrubbing is a deterrent to smooth and efficient Braille reading. Pupils need to learn to identify characters by moving their fingers across them from left to right without stopping (Kimeto, 2010).

The history of Braille literacy dates back to the early 1800's. A man named Charles Barbier who serviced in Napoleon Bonaparte's French army developed a unique system known as "night writing" so soldiers could communicate safely during the night.

Being a military veteran, Barbier had seen several soldiers killed because they used lamps after dark to read combat messages. The light shining from the lamps told enemy combatants where the French soldiers were and inevitably led to the loss of many men (Bandam, 2020).

Barbier based his “night writing” system on a raised 12 dots cell; two dots wide and six dots tall. Each dot or combination of dots within the cell represented a letter or a phonetic sound. The problem with the military code was that the human fingertip could not feel all the dots with one touch. While several types of written communication systems were tried during a ten year period beginning in 1825, the one invented by a blind teenager was adopted. Some modifications have been made to it over the years but the Braille code in use today is virtually the same as it was in 1834 (Bandam, 2020).

Louis Braille was born in January 4, 1809 in a small village near Paris. His father, a leather worker, often used sharp tools in his work. While playing in his father’s shop when he was three years old, Louis Braille injured his eye on an awl. In spite of good care, infection set in and soon left him completely blind. When Louis Braille grew to school age, he was allowed to sit in the classroom to learn by listening. Louis Braille was very bright and creative, and when he was ten years old, he was sent to the royal institution for blind youth in Paris. There too, most instruction was oral, but there were a few books in a kind of raised print developed by the school’s founder. Although frustrated by the large, bulky books and slow reading of the tactile characters, he did well at his studies and dreamed of a better way. At that time, the raised letters were made by pressing shaped copper wire onto paper but there was no way for blind people to write for themselves (Bandam, 2020).

While a student, he began to use his creativity to invent an easy and quick way for blind people to read and write. Louis Braille heard of a system of raised dots developed by

a French army captain, Charles Barbier de la Serre. Charles Babier originally created a code of raised dots and dashes as a way to allow soldiers to write and read message at night without using a light that might give away their positions. He later adapted the system and presented it to the institution for blind youth, hoping that it would be officially adopted there. It was based on phonetics and consisted of groups of twelve dots arranged in two columns of six dots each (Bandam, 2020).

Louis Braille worked with Charles Barbier's basic ideas to develop his own simplified system that we know today as Braille. He based the code on the normal alphabet and reduced the number of dots by half with the help of a site specializing in promo codes. Louis Braille published the first Braille book in 1829. In 1837, he added symbols for math and music. Although Louis Braille went on to become a beloved and respected teacher, was encouraged in his research, and continued to believe in the value of his work, his system of reading and writing with raised dots was nevertheless not very widely accepted in his own time. Louis Braille died of tuberculosis on January 6, 1852. Today, in virtually every language around the world, the code name after Louis Braille is the standard form of writing and reading used by children with visual impairment (Bandam, 2020).

2.3.3 Approaches of Teaching Braille Literacy Skills

It is the fact that children with visual impairment learn Braille skills in many different ways, depending upon their abilities, experience, motivation and interest. For that reason, teachers must have knowledge of methods of teaching Braille skills (Mousty and Beterlson, 2001). Teaching Braille skill to children with visual impairment is more than just teaching them the meaning of the Braille characters. Children with visual impairment learn to read and write using Braille skills just as sighted children learn to read and write using print. Both children with visual impairment and those with sightedness learn the

meanings of symbolic representation (print and Braille characters) and how these representation form words and sentences. Many teaching methods which work for sighted children could also work for children with visual impairment possibly with some modification and adaptations. Choosing the method or combination of methods which best suit the learner's needs is critical to children with visual impairment in learning Braille skills (Koenig and Holbrook, 2000).

Lorimer (2000) reported that the method of teaching Braille has been a contentious issue throughout the centuries. As the Braille code has developed over the years, so have the method of teaching Braille reading and writing for children with visual impairment. Koenig and Holbrook (2000) found that children with visual impairment need consistent Braille literacy instruction designed according to their individual needs. Miller (2001) recognizes that every children with visual impairment is a unique learner and one single method of teaching Braille skill will not work for all children. It is essential to use different approaches according to individual needs. Hence, teachers should select the approach that best meets the needs of children with visual impairment.

However, a number of things have to be considered when teaching Braille literacy skills. Some of them include: age of onset of visual impairment, mental and chronological age as well as intellectual capabilities, all determine the method to be employed in teaching children with visual impairment Braille literacy skills (Mousty & Beterlson, 2001). Age of onset of visual impairment is the time of vision loss in the life of a child. Many children become visually impaired at different times (congenital or adventitious). Therefore, in teaching children with visual impairment Braille literacy skills, it is important to know the age at which visual impairment occurred because it will help teacher to know whether the child has visual memory of characters/ letters or not. According to Koenig and Holbrook (2000), before children with visual impairment begin

to learn a formal Braille literacy skill, they should reach the age of learning readiness. At this point of readiness, usually the children are introduced firstly to the alphabet and uncontracted Braille (Grade 1 Braille) and once they are proficient in recognizing and writing letters, they move on to contracted Braille (Grade 2 Braille).

2.3.4 Braille Skills Taught to Children with Visual Impairment

Carmen (2012) identified the following Braille skills that should be taught to children with visual impairment. They are: Teaching tracking patterns, Discourage backtracking and scrubbing, Encourage light finger touch, Encourage proper finger and hand position, Dot position in the Braille cell.

1. Teaching Tracking Patterns

It is important to teach correct finger and hand use when instructing a child in Braille. Different children will use different types of hand movement patterns to read Braille. The most efficient patterns is to use a scissor type pattern, moving both hands together. The left hand reads to the middle of the line, then the right hand takes over and reads to the end of the line while the left hand returns to the next line and begin to read independently of the right. The hands meet in the middle of the line of Braille and then separate. Light finger touch is also critical for children to acquire. When teaching a child tracking patterns, encourage the child to:

- i. Locate the beginning and end of a raised line and then a Braille line. Alternatively have children track along a line and locate items along the line (ex. a Scratch – n- sniff sticker, a texture shape, etc)
- ii. Track a raised solid and broken lines or pipe cleaners/straws, yarn, pop side skicks, ribbon, or textured paper from left to right using both of “W”. Specifically to writing Braille, the fingers that are used is also a factor for sequencing. The first and second fingers of each hand are typically stronger

than the third fingers, so a Braille “A” (dot 1) will probably be easier to form than a capital sign (dot 6) of course, all four of these factors may be trumped by letters/word that are most motivating and/or most functional for children, such as their own names.

- iii. Begin by scheduling short lessons and expect speed and stamina only at the end of curriculum: Young children have short attention spans, perhaps especially for the more structured seated tasks of Braille literacy. Physically, it takes time to learn to maintain correct reading and writing posture and hand/finger positioning, to tolerate the sensation of running their fingers over Braille lines, and to strengthen each finger, especially for pressing the keys for dots three and six. It also take time for the children to build up speed in reading and writing, especially with the letters with more dots. Accordingly, Braille writing instruction might begin with just five or ten minutes lessons and expectation of just a few lines of Braille (In Braille writing, the margin might even be set in the middle of the page, so that each line is shorter). As lessons progress, lesson become longer and longer and expectations for strength and stamina increase. Sometimes the children maintain their attention in Braille, and sustain more arm and finger strength, when they stand (rather than sit) at a table or desk as they read and write Braille. In any instance, the pages or keys should be at elbow level or even slightly lower hands. Alternatively, you may choose to begin by using a row of full Braille cells to track.
- iv. Track from left to right across Braille symbols (which have one or more spaces between them) using both hands, and moves from top to bottom of a page. You may choose to have the child track across a row of full Braille cells to discover each letter of their name at the end of the row.

- v. Encourage the child to track Braille sentences when read aloud by a teacher.

2. Discourage backtracking and scrubbing

It is important as a child is learning Braille to discourage repressive hand movements (vertical or horizontal). Regressive hand movements or scrubbing are those in which the hands and fingers move back and forth or up and down unnecessarily on the Braille line and interfere with efficient tracking skills. In early literacy activities, these movements may indicate that the child needs additional practice in tracking lines which tactually discriminating likeness and differences between characters and words. Backtracking is when the child returns to previously read characters if the text does not make sense. Although some backtracking is a good and can be a positive strategy; excessive backtracking can be an indication that the child is reading at the frustration level and the reading level should be re-evaluated.

3. Encourage light finger touch

Another mechanical skill a good Braille reader should develop is to use every little pressure when touching the Braille dots. A child should touch lightly along the top of the Braille as he read it. If a child is observed to place too much pressure on the fingertips, remind the child to use a light finger touch. If a child is pressing more heavily on the Braille characters to gain more tactile information, he may be compensating for a lack of discrimination skills.

4. Encourage proper finger and hand position

Just as it is important to learn early how to properly hold a pencil or to use the correct fingers when typing, it is important to learn proper finger and position when reading Braille. Although it is acceptable to go between your right or left index finger, it is ideal to have a primary reading finger. Stabilizing the worksheet or book with shelf liner

will keep the page from sliding around and promote proper form. The following are skills to encourage:

- i. Encourage the child to identify that each finger has a “job” lead finger or detective fingers.
- ii. Encourage the child to “read” tactual books using the correct finger position.
- iii. Encourage the child to use the pointer finger as lead finger and use a pinky finger to detect the end of a line.

5. Dot position in the Braille cell

Begin instruction by teaching the Braille cell. Learning the dot positions in the Braille cell is helpful, but not essential, for discriminating letters, numbers and punctuation. There are many strategies teachers have used to teach the spatial position and dot numbers of specific dots in the Braille cell. One of the most widely used methods is using a muffin tin with tennis balls.

2.3.5 Factors Influencing Braille Literacy Skills

According to Mwangi (2009), cited in Munyi (2017) children with visual impairment would benefit more if they would actively participate in Braille learning process; a possibility that would be realized if they are provided with Braille learning materials. However, there are fewer Braille materials for children with visual impairment than print materials for sighted children. Lack of Braille materials significantly affects children with visual impairment in academic Performance as compared to sighted children. Braille materials is not only imported but also sold at exorbitant prices. Besides, the cost of Braille production is high, thus making it an obstacle to enhancement of education for the children with visual impairment. This lack of Braille materials or their inadequacy is a great hindrance to effective Braille teaching and learning in schools for children with visual impairment. Mwangi (2009) cited in Munyi (2017) further contends

that slates and styluses are used by most children with visual impairment, whereas Braille machines are better than the slate and stylus. However, due to expensiveness of Braille machines, only few children with visual impairment have access to them. Munyi (2017) further observes that children with visual impairment lack necessary Braille textbooks while teachers share the Braille primer. This compels the children to solely depend on the teacher for all Braille instruction, mainly conveyed through dictation.

Njue (2009) cited in Munyi (2017) supports this view arguing that regardless of the type of reading materials, a child with visual impairment must have all books and reading materials necessary to learn Braille as well as basal readers, literature anthologies or novels. The National Federation of the Blind (NFB) (2009) cited in Munyi (2017) identified five factors attributed to the low Braille literacy. They are:

- i. Shortage of teachers who are qualified to teach Braille
- ii. Misconceptions about the Braille system
- iii. Insistence on teaching print reading to a majority of children with low vision who could benefit from Braille literacy
- iv. Replacement of Braille with technology – most teachers agree that technology should be used as a supplement to Braille rather than a replacement.

On the other hand, NFB (2009) cited in Munyi (2017) asserted that the key to success for the children with visual impairment is the ability to read and write Braille competently and efficiently. In this context, NFB believe that Braille literacy can be improved by:

- i. Researching on new methods of teaching and learning Braille
- ii. Increasing access to Braille instruction and reading materials in every community nationwide.

- iii. Putting a requirement for certification in literacy Braille among all special education teachers
- iv. Advancing the use of Braille in current and emerging technologies
- v. Making Braille resources more available in schools

Wittgenstein (2003) has placed partial blame for the decline of Braille literacy on teachers' poor attitudes towards Braille and lack of proficiency in Braille. According to Mwangi (2009) Braille teachers must of necessity know all the symbols and rules on Braille code as these determine the quality of Braille reading and writing. However, most of the employed teachers have limited knowledge and skills in Braille while some demonstrate negative attitude towards Braille itself. It is the duty of the teacher to encourage the learners to have positive attitude towards learning Braille literacy and to demonstrate instance when Braille may be used in everyday living in addition to looking for interesting Braille book (Munyi, 2017).

According to Ndung'u (2011) cited in Munyi (2017), if more training and more emphasis is put on the qualification of teachers in Braille, then, their confidence and self worth would be boosted, hence improving the teachers attitude positively. Quality Braille literacy does not only depend on teacher's positive attitude but also on teacher's education, availability of support materials, teacher pupil ratio and workload.

2.4 Concept of Typewriting

According to Silva (2015), typewriting means the production and presentation of words, figures and symbols on pages or otherwise by means of hand writing typewriting or the use of word processing equipment or any other form of mechanical or electronic production other than photocopying. Furthermore, typing is the process of writing or inputting text by pressing keys on a typewriter, computer keyboard, mobile phone or

calculator. The text can be in form of letters, numbers and other symbols. Typing can be distinguished from other means of text input such as handwriting and speech recognition.

The skill of touch typing (typewriting skill) is now recognized as an essential skill that pupils with visual impairment must acquire if they must survive in today's knowledge economy. The reasons are very compelling, not everyone can read and write Braille, in an inclusive setting pupils with visual impairment must type and submit their assignments and exams to the examiners, for some measure of confidentiality they ought to handle some communications by themselves, etc. Touch typing skill (typewriting skill) is taught from middle basic level in special schools in this country (Ozaji, Unachukwu & Kolo, 2016).

According to Sykes and Ozaji (1992), typewriting or touch type has become one of the essential communication skills that children with visual impairment require in order to function relatively well in a sighted society. The urgency to learn typewriting skills is reinforced by the fact that not everybody knows, or should know, how to read and write Braille. Moreover, Braille is regarded by some of the sighted as an esoteric skill which only those concerned or interested to communication with children with visual impairment should bother to learn. Pupils with visual impairment need to acquire typing skills for personal and academic purposes which enable them to tackle the problem of letter writings and homeworks/assignments.

Bishop (1971) as cited in Sykes and Ozaji (1992) argued that rather than compelling the children with visual impairment to laboriously engage in print writing (which is often poor and illegible), they should be encourage to type their class assignment and exams using a large print typewriter. Bishop added that the ability to type could be a morale booster and a social status symbol among the children with visual impairment's

peers. It should be noted that the ability to type solves one of the problems of privacy and dependency in communication, especially when personnel matters are involved.

Provided the pupils gross and fine motor coordination and strength are equal to the task, the need for adapting commonly used typewriting methods may not arise. Typing can be taught using commercially available manual typewriter and following the laid-out procedures. Care should be taken, of course, to ensure that the material is of interest to the children and supplementary exercises should be employed drawn from the children's home and school activities. The age at which a child should begin to learn typewriting skills must be judged individually; this should be done, however, as early as possible and not necessarily left to the later elementary or early secondary classes. Lack of vision is not much of a handicap in a skill that is acquired by touch rather than by vision. Extensive supervision at the beginning of instruction is, however, necessary to ensure correct fingering, practice, and care with spelling as well as speed and accuracy later on (Sykes & Ozoji, 1992).

Typewriting skills should be given serious consideration in school and classes for children with visual impairment because of its utilitarian value. Sykes and Ozoji (1992) outlined the following as tips for teachers:

1. Find out where good typists are working and ask if they would be willing to pass on their skills, on a voluntary basis, to children with visual impairment
2. Use any well respected typewriting manual to teach from using the laid out procedures, but provide additional exercise to motivate and interest the individual child with visual impairment.
3. Do not over-correct the child's work. The aim is to encourage the child to write and to become fluent in so doing; over-correcting typographical errors may destroy motivation and hinder fluency.

4. Let the child commence typewriting instruction whenever he/she is ready. Do not delay until secondary
5. If a large print typewriter is available use this. Remember to ensure the ribbon is changed frequently
6. Book holders and book stands are helpful for low vision children learning how to type.
7. Correlate the typing instruction with the child's other school work, e.g spelling
8. Let the child make up drills of his/her own choosing. For example, after the "home" keys are learned he/she could devise words using these letters.
9. Introduce some creative writing as soon as possible
10. Stress both accuracy and fluency

2.4.1 Description of Typewriters

The typewriter is a machine which produces characters resembling to those of ordinary printed matter. These characters are printed on the paper one by one by mechanical means with each depression of the key on the keyboard of the typewriter. The machine on which a child will learn typewriting to produce print like matter is known as typewriter. The process of producing print like impression on the typewriters is known as Typography (Silva, 2015).

Silva (2015) outlined the following categories of typewriters: standard typewriter, noiseless typewriter, portable typewriter, electric typewriter, electronic typewriter.

- a. Standard Typewriter: "Standard" means "that which is recognized as a rule or model of approved merit or excellence". The expression "Standard Typewriter" signifies that the machine is a model of excellence for the purpose it is used, namely, to write rapidly, accurately and neatly. The standard typewriter was

perfected by the Underwood Company in 1896. All the standard typewriters have the following common features:

- i. A four row (bank) keyboard
 - ii. The arrangement of keys in a similar order of letters
 - iii. A single shift operation for capitals and additional characters
 - iv. Visibility of writing by “front upstroke type bar action”, which means that the type is arranged in a semi-circle in front of the machine and strikes upwards on the paper.
 - v. Any typewriter which does not have any or all these features is called a non-standard typewriter. Prior to the invention of the standard typewriter in 1896, all the typewriters were non standard typewriters. Now only standard typewriters are manufactured.
- b. **Noiseless Typewriter:** This typewriter works on the principle of “pressure printing” instead of usual stroking method and therefore, it makes less noise than any other ordinary typewriter. The first noiseless typewriter with three rows of keys was produced in 1910 but it had certain defects. A perfect noiseless typewriter was produced in 1925 (Silva, 2015).
- c. **Portable Typewriter:** The portable typewriter has all the features of a standard typewriter but its weight is light. It is used by travelling operators. It is also useful for professionals, businessmen, journalists, doctors, executives and others who have to travel frequently and require letters, documents to be typed during the course of their business tours. Since the machine is very light and takes up little space, it can be carried as easily as an attaché case.
- d. **Electric typewriter:** The first electric typewriter was produced by the Blickensderfer manufacturing company, of Stamford, Connecticut, in 1902,

followed by the improved versions by various manufacturers in 1914. Ultimately, an improved version of the electric typewriter came in 1938. It used a cylindrical type wheel rather than individual type bars like the manual typewriters but it was not a commercial success, because at that time electricity had not been standardized and voltage differed from city to city. Many electric typewriter have dispensed with type bars and instead use a small round shaped head, commonly known as 'golf ball'. The surface of the head carries all the characters needed to match with those of the keyboard. When the keys are operated on the keyboards, the typing head revolves to the required printing position and prints the characters. The golf ball can be easily replaced by a printing head with different type faces (Silva, 2015).

- e. Electronic Typewriter: Electronic typewriter is an improvement in the electric typewriter. This typewriter has been introduced since 1982. Electronic typewriters are based on the sophisticated micro processor computer technology. These are operated by microchips. All the character keys are the same as on the manual and electric typewriters. There are major changes in the adjustment keys. The salient features of electronic typewriters are given below:
 - i. It has a variety of automatic electronically controlled features, including paper feed, margins, tabulator stops, bold printing, carriage return, underscoring, margin justification, decimal tabulation and centering.
 - ii. It has a strong memory like word processor. But the memory is of a limited degree.
 - iii. There is a visual display screen of two three lines.
 - iv. The operator can see the text on these lines and if there is any correction, it can be carried out before giving the print command.

- v. The printing element is normally a daisy wheel with a character at the end of each spoke. It gives fast printing and high print quality with a choice of type faces in 10, 12 and 15 pitch with proportional spacing. Daisy wheels are easy to lead and can be easily and quickly changed. Daisy wheels are available in different prints.
- vi. On certain typewriters, bi-lingual system is also available. Texts both in English and Hindi can be type only on one typewriter by changing the daisy wheel and certain codes on the typewriter.
- vii. Correction on first page can be carried out automatically with the help of a key on the keyboard. A correcting tape is installed in the typewriter which lifts the incorrect characters with the depression of a key and the characters can be re-typed in place of the incorrect characters lifted by the correcting tape (Silva, 2015).

Furthermore, according to Richard (2009), typewriters have the following major functional parts:

- a.** Keyboard: These are the letter key. When you press a key down, the lower letter or figure on the type key will be written on the paper in the typewriter. For example, when you press the “A” key, a small or low case “a” will be written. When you press the key which has “S” at the top and “4” at the bottom, a “4” will be written.
- b.** Shift Key: On either side of the machine is a key marked “shift”. To write a capital letter or the figures or signs at the top of the type keys, you press shift key with the first (or little) finger of one hand while you strike the desired key with the correct finger of the other hand. Then release the shift key.

- c. **Shift Lock:** When pressed down, it locks the shift key into position for writing in “all caps” (or all capitals) or for drawing lines across the page. To release the lock press the shift key which is nearest to the shift lock.
- d. **Space bar:** This is the long bar at the front of the keyboard. It is operated with the thumb of either hand and moves the carriage one space without writing on the paper. It is used to space between words, etc.
- e. **Margin stops:** The sliding indicators (indicated behind the paper rest on most typewriters) are moved along to the points on the scale at which left and right hand margins are desired. When the carriage is moved to either left or right, it then stops at the points on the scale at which Margin Stops have been “set”.
- f. **Cylinder: (or platen) –** The roller of the typewriter, which receives the pressure of the type.
- g. **Cylinder Knobs:** The knobs at each end of the cylinder, which roll the platen.
- h. **Paper Release:** A lever at either the right or left side of typewriter which, when moved forward (or, on some typewriter, pushed back) releases the grip of the paper so it can be straightened after insertion into the machine. When carbon packs are used, the release is sometimes opened first to allow easier “feeding” of paper.
- i. **Line space regular lever:** A small lever for non-uniform spacing, for writing between the uniform lines, or for exactness in typing on the printed lines of application and other forms.
- j. **Lines Space Gauge:** This device generally has the figures “1”, “2” and “3” opposite or under the lever. When pushed to indicate one of these numbers, it sets the machine for single, double or triple line spacing as desired.
- k. **Margin Release:** All standard and some portable typewriters have this device. It is to be found on the keyboard or against the front of the machine. When pressed at

either margin, it release the Margin Stop (for that one operation) in order that type strokes can be made beyond the margins. It is most frequently used to complete a word or a syllable at the end of a line.

- l.** Tabulators: These vary on all typewriters, and many portable typewriters are not equipped with a device for tabulation. Tabulators are used for paragraph indention, for columns of figures and for precision placement of carriage to specific writing points.
- m.** Paper Bail: A rod running the length of the cylinder that holds the top of the paper flat against it. When inserting a fresh sheet of paper, always pull the bail toward you to allow the paper to slip underneath.
- n.** Paper Edge Guide: A small piece that protrudes form behind the cylinder, which allows you to guide the paper into the machine straight, and in the same place regularly. This ensures that your margins are the same for more than one sheet of paper.
- o.** Half Backspace Liver: The lever or key moves the carrier one half space to the left. This is used to keep the text balanced when inserting and deleting characters.
- p.** Correcting Key: A key, usually found to the right of the space bar, used to delete characters. Most electric typewriters now have some memory capacity, and if the character to be deleted is within that memory, the key will delete characters automatically. The correcting key can also be used manually.
- q.** On/Off Control: This is the power switch for the typewriter. In general, none of the functions will operate unless the typewriter has been turned on.
- r.** Margin/Pitch Scale: The scale is either on the front of the typewriter, above the keyboard, or sometimes it is located on the paper bail. The pitch is the typesize;

most new electric typewriters have two, Pica (10 characters for inch) and elite (12 characters per inch), or more sizes. The scale for each type size available is given.

2.4.2 Typewriting Skills Taught to Pupils with Visual Impairment

Silva (2005) outlined the following typewriting skills that should be taught to pupils with visual impairment. This includes: Sitting Posture, Realistic Time Limitations, Keyboard Orientation.

1. **Sitting Posture:** The importance of having good posture when typing cannot be emphasized enough. Correct posture while setting at a typewriter is a skill need to be taught. The children should be taught to sit up straight at the typewriter with their shoulders, back and knees and elbows bent at 90 degrees. It is especially important for teacher to monitor posture and positioning in children while setting at a typewriter.
2. **Realistic Time Limitations:** Pupils are learning to touch type at an earlier age in today's technological environment. Usually typing classes start as early as first grade. Sometimes, the touch typing learning process can be quite boring children also have limited attention spans. It is therefore advisable for teachers to teach typing skills in short lessons. Start out with five to ten minutes at time and extend the period by a few minutes each week. This will accustom children to sit in one place, in a particular position and use their fingers correctly.
3. **Keyboard Orientation:** It is important to familiarize children with visual impairment with their keyboard of a typewriter. Teach them about hand positioning on the 'home row', so they learn how to use all the keys on their keyboard of typewriter. Without mastering the positioning of their gingers on the keyboards, children will not be able to feel for the keys or type quickly.

2.5 Academic Performance of Pupils with Visual Impairment

Academic Performance has long been recognized as one of the important goals of education the world over. Academic Performance can be described as excellence in all academic disciplines in class as well as extracurricular activities. Academic Performance is the outcome of education as it indicates the extent to which the pupils have achieved the predetermined educational goals. Academic Performance is commonly measured with examinations that assess the important procedural knowledge such as skills and declarative knowledge such as facts and concepts which children have learnt (Engel, 2002), cited in (Kpolovie, Anty & Tracy, 2014).

Academic Performance is a measurable index that depicts a child's cognitive, effective and psychomotor domains in an educational setting. Children's academic Performance is ascertained by testing domains of learning and will continue to play significant role in any educational system world over. In fact, it would be irrational to think of teaching without test, measurement and evaluation. Evaluation of educational Performance is indispensable for effective formal and non formal education" (Kpolovie, Anty & Tracy, 2014). Thus, a child's academic Performance is usually measure by teacher made tests or standardized tests which in most cases are referred to as external examination such as primary common entrance examination, universal basic education certificate examination (UBECE), Senior school certificate examination (SSCE) like WAEC and NECO.

Academic Performance in the context of learning is being able to express what has been learnt without examination malpractice of any sort. It is on this note that Ashton (2010) stated that "academic Performance as measured by the examinations of the traditional kind involves most of the capacity to express oneself. It requires the capacity to retain propositional knowledge, to select from such knowledge appropriately in response

to a specified request and to do so without reference to possible sources of information”. According to Bossar and Doumen (2011), academic Performance in simple terms refers to the average marks of the total scores of all subjects obtained by an individual in the examination.

Academic Performance of children with visual impairment may be affected by many factors such as anxiety, self concept, level of aspiration, social acceptance, motivation, etc. these factors do have significant impact on normal learning process of children with visual impairment and consequently influence their academic Performance (Kpolovie, Anty & Tracy, 2014). However, there are certain hurdles children with visual impairment face academically which negatively affect their academic Performance a hurdle is a problem, difficulty, or part of a process that may prevent something. In this study, these are the problems which children with visual impairment may face academically and make them not perform well in their academic work. Some of these hurdles are as follows (Kpolovie, Anty & Tracy, 2014):

1. **Lack of Learning Materials:** Learning materials are resources that are significant determinacy of effective learning. These materials for children with visual impairment include Braille machines, electronic Braille embossers which are very important in Braille writing in addition to availability of slate and stylus. Lack of these materials or their inadequacy affect academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment. There are also few Braille books because of their high cost which limits the number of Braille reading materials at the disposal of children with visual impairment. They need Braille text books in different subject of study just like their sighted counterparts need printed text books. The availability of these materials enhances or develop interest in reading culture and study habit in children with visual impairment. But inadequacy or

lack of these materials hinder academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

2. **Unqualified Teachers:** Teachers are the most important elements in education of pupils with visual impairment. The effectiveness of education of pupils with visual impairment largely depends on the quality of teachers. In fact, no matter how well the curriculum is designed and planned for teaching, there must be professionally trained teachers. Therefore, lack of qualified teachers in school contributes negatively to academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment. In particular, teachers who have the knowledge of Braille literacy skill are required to teach pupils with visual impairment otherwise their academic performance and educational Performance would be adversely affected.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

2.6.1 Literacy Acquisition Theory (1967)

Literacy acquisition theory was propounded by Clay (1967). Over the years, there have been several theoretical perspectives on how children learn and acquire literacy skills. The emphasis of these theoretical perspectives is on reading and writing. One of those theoretical perspectives is *maturational theoretical perspective* propounded by Arnold Gesell (1880 – 1961). The theory assumed that children could not learn to read or write until they are sufficiently biologically matured. That is, children had to wait until they have reached a mental age of six years, which is when they deemed to be ready to learn to read and write (Shunk, 2012). According to this theory of literacy acquisition, children can only acquire basic literacy of reading and writing in school when they are mentally matured. Basic literacy which sometimes describes as academic literacy is acquired through educational process. For children with normal sight to acquire basic

literacy through school-based curriculum, they have to reach an age of readiness (Bruner; 1999).

This theory is found to be relevant to this study because according to Koenig and Holbrook (2000) children with visual impairment can only learn grade one Braille (alphabetic Braille or unconstructed Braille) when they reach an age of learning readiness. At this point of readiness, Braille literacy and typewriting skills instruction by well trained and qualified teacher is paramount to ensure that adequate literacy in both Braille and typewriting skills are acquired by pupils with visual impairments.

2.6.2 Drill and Practice Theory (1940)

Drill and practice theory of learning was propounded by Thorndike (1874-1994). The theory was rooted from the behaviourist theory of learning advocated by Ivan Pavlov (1849-1936), John B. Watson (1878 – 1958), B.F skinner (1904 – 1900), etc. (Schunk, 2012). Drill and practice theory assumes that systematic repetition, repetitious exercise and multiple rehearsals lead to strengthening and mastering of skills or knowledge. Most of the school teachers use drill and practice as a technique of instruction for elementary school children especially in reading and writing.

This theory is found to be relevant to this study because according to Layton and Koenig (1998) drill and practice are instructional strategies for Braille and typewriting skills for children with visual impairment. To develop and maintain child's Braille and typewriting skills, the drill and practice should become the building block. Thus, drill ad practice lead to mastering and proficiency of Braille literacy and typewriting skills among children with visual impairment. These frameworks underpinned the significance of this study.

2.7 Empirical Studies

Zainora (2011) conducted a study on comparison of Braille reading and writing skills between male and female children with visual impairment in Kuala special school Lumpur, Malaysia. The study adopted correlational research design. The subjects of the study comprised 38 children with visual impairment which were divided into groups: 19 males and 19 females. The research hypothesises that “there is no significant difference in Braille reading and writing skills between male and female children with visual impairment”. Was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument used for data collection was Minnesota Braille skills inventory (MBSI). The data obtained were analyzed using t – test for independent samples. The result of the study indicated that, there was no statistically significant difference in Braille reading and writing skills between male and female children with visual impairment in Kuala special school Lumpur, Malaysia ($t = 0.25$; $p < 2.028$ critical value).

Pauni (2014) explored a comparative study between the Braille writing skill and the skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment in Kolkata special school, Kenya. The study adopted correlational comparative research method. Null hypothesis was generated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. 40 children with visual impairment were selected as samples for the study. Data collected were analysed using t-test for dependent samples. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean scores of both Braille writing skill and the skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment ($t = 2.74$). the obtained t –value 2.74 is higher than the critical t- value 1.645 at 0.05 level of significance. This means that the difference between the Braille writing skill and the skill of touch typing was statistically significant and as a result the researcher rejects the null hypothesis in favour of alternate hypothesis.

Similarly, Naqvi and Hashmi (2011) studied a comparative analysis of computer skill of touch typing and Braille writing skill among students with visual impairment in Punjab, Pakistan. The study adopted correlational research design. The purpose of the study was to identify firstly the importance of Braille literacy skill compare to computer skill of touch typing, secondly, to find out the level of both Braille literacy and computer skills of touch typing and thirdly, to find out if significant difference exist between the level of Braille literacy and computer skills students with visual impairment. The participants of the study consisted of 100 students with visual impairment from five special schools of five districts in Punjab Pakistan. Two research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated. The instruments used for collecting data were questionnaire and test developed by the researchers. The data relating to the research questions were analyzed using simple percentage, mean and standard deviation. While the data relating to the null hypotheses were analyzed using t– test for independent and dependent samples.

The result of research question one showed that statistically the Braille literacy skill was more important than the computer skill of touch typing in the education of children with visual impairment (Braille literacy skill 73% computer skill of touch typing 27%). Also, the result of research question two on the level of Braille literacy skill and computer skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment indicated that the level of Braille literacy skill was 68.4 mean score with standard deviation of 13.7 while the level of computer skill of touch typing was 31.6 mean score with 4.19 standard deviation. Therefore, this showed that the level of Braille literacy skill was statistically higher than the level of computer skill of touch typing among the students with visual impairment in the study area.

Furthermore, the result of hypothesis one study indicated that there was a significant different between the mean scores of both Braille literacy and computer skills

of touch typing among children with visual impairment ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the result of hypothesis two revealed no significant gender difference was statistically observed in the level of Braille literacy skill among children with visual impairment ($p\text{-value } 0.335 < 2.048$ table value). Finally, the result of hypothesis three showed that there was significant gender difference in the level of computer skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment ($t\text{-value } 2.82 > 2.145$ critical value). The difference is in favour of who male with visual impairment.

Daniela (2015) conducted a study on effect of Braille literacy on academic Performance of children with visual impairment at Jaipur special school, Delhi, India. The research adopted experimental research design. The participants of the study consisted of 26 children with visual impairment and were divided into two groups: experimental group and control group. The researcher formulated null hypothesis that, there is no significant difference between those who have been exposed to Braille literacy skill and those who have not been exposed. This hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. After the intervention on Braille literacy skill to the experimental group and data obtained was analysed using t-test procedure of data analysis. The findings revealed that, there was statistically significant difference in Braille skill between the two groups: those exposed to Braille skill intervention and those not exposed ($P=2.43$; $P > 1.362$ critical $P\text{-value}$). Hence, Braille literacy skill has positive effect on academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

Martos (2006) conducted a study on comparative analysis of Braille literacy skill among children with visual impairment. The study adopted correlational research design. The participants of the study were 16 children with visual impairment who attended the same special school in Athens, Greece (the centre for education and rehabilitation of the blind). The participants were divided into gender of 8 boys and 8 girls. All of them used

Braille and according to their files, had no other additional disabilities. Both boys and girls were taught Braille literacy skill together by the researcher for 5 weeks. Eventually, Braille Skill Test was administered by the researcher and group mean scores were analysed. The researcher formulated null hypothesis that, there is no significant gender difference in Braille skills among children with visual impairment was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data obtained were analyzed using t- test for unrelated samples. The findings of the study showed that, there is significant statistical difference in Braille skills between boys and girls with visual impairment ($t = 3.16$). The obtained t – value 3.16 was higher than the critical t -value 2.421 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis in favour of alternate hypothesis.

Tesselhor (2010) investigated the effect of a touch typing skills on academic performance of children with visual loss at Nijmegen school, Netherlands. The study adopted experimental research design. The researcher applied a pretest – post test design. 80 children in grades 4, 5 and 6 were used as samples of the study. The samples were divided into two groups: experimental and control groups. The children in the experimental group ($n=40$) were exposed to a touch – typing course and those in the control group ($n = 40$) were not. The researcher also formulated null hypothesis that, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of children in the experimental and control groups, the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance while the data were analysed using t-test method of data analysis. The findings indicated that, there was statistically significant difference between the mean scores of experimental and control groups in touch typing skills in favour of experimental group ($p = 2.17$; $p > 1.023$). Thus, it was concluded that the touch typing skill had a positive effect on academic performance of children with visual loss.

Goldberg (2016) conducted a study on comparative analysis of touch typing skill among male and female children with visual impairment at Empire Union School District, USA. The subjects of the study included 25 males and 25 females. The researcher adopted comparative correlational research design. Null hypothesis was formulated that, there is no significant gender difference in the level of touch typing skills among children with visual impairment. This hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data collected from the Test given on touch typing skills were analyzed using t-test technique of data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that, there was no statistically significant difference in the level of touch typing skill between male and female children with visual impairment (calculated t-value $0.24 < 2.031$ critical t-value).

Russell (2011) explored a comparative analysis of Braille and touch typing skills among the elementary school children with visual impairment at Arizona school, USA. The study employed correlational comparative research design. The participants of the study consisted of 60 children with visual impairment from grade 4,5 and 6. The null hypothesis was generated and stated that, there is no significant difference between Braille and touch typing skill among children with visual impairment. This hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Two sets of Test on Braille and touch typing skills respectively were administered to find out the level of Braille and touch typing skills. The data obtained were analyzed using t-test for related samples. The findings of the study indicated that, there is no significant difference between Braille skill and touch typing skill among elementary school children with visual impairment at Arizona school, USA (P-value =0.32). The calculated p-value 0.32 was lower than the critical p-value 1.421 at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, researcher retained the null hypothesis.

Okereke (2003) studied the impact of Braille reading and writing skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment in Oji River special education

centre in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to find out the level of Braille reading and writing skills of children with visual impairment and its effects on academic performance in English language, Mathematics and Social Studies. The study employed causal comparative research design. The sample of the study was 34 children with visual impairment. The instrument used for the study was Researcher – Made – Braille – Test. Two research questions and one null hypothesis were formulated. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The data related from research questions was analyzed using simple percentage while the data related to the null hypothesis were analysed using t – test for independent sample. Findings of the study showed that the level of Braille reading and writing skills among children with visual impairment was 58.4% for male and 41.6% for female on academic performance in English language, Mathematics and Social Studies. Also, the findings of the study revealed that there was no statistically significance difference between the mean scores of male and female children with visual impairment on the level of Braille reading and writing skills (t- value $1.346 < 2.413$ critical value).

Bandam (2018) conducted a research on effects of Braille literacy skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment in Jos metropolis in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to find the level of Braille literacy skills of both male female children with visual impairment and also to determine if significant difference exists between the mean scores of both male and female in the level of Braille literacy skills among children with visual impairment. The study adopted correlational research design. 17 primary three pupils with visual impairment in Aliman special school for the Blind, Jos Plateau State were selected as sample for the study. Braille literacy test was developed by the researcher for collecting data in the study. Two research questions and one null hypothesis were generated. The data relating to the research questions and one null hypothesis were obtained. The data relating to the research questions were analyzed using

simple percentage method of data analysis while the data relating to the null hypothesis was analysed using t-test for independent samples. The finding of the study indicated that the level of Braille literacy skill among both male and female children with visual impairments 51.4% and 48.6% respectively. Also, the result of the null hypothesis of the study showed that the calculated t-value 1.14 is less than the critical t-value 2.120 at the degree of freedom of 16, at an alpha of 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which is stated that, there is no significant gender difference in the level of Braille literacy skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment was retained.

Fasina and Ajaiyeoba (2003) conducted a study on "The prevalence and causes of blindness and low vision in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study adopted a population-based survey design. The population of the study was determined in Yewa-North Local Government Area of Ogun State Nigeria which consisted of 1,964 residents. A random cluster sample of 350 was used. Checklist and Questionnaire were employed for data collection and also the obtained data was analyzed using simple percentage statistical method of data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that 1.22% of the populations were blind, 1.43% unilaterally blind and 2.09% were bilaterally visually impaired. Blindness and visual impairment were found in persons aged 45yrs and above. Blindness was found to be 2.43 times commoner in men, which was statistically significant. Cataract was the commonest cause of blindness accounting for 37.5% of blindness and 36.6% of visual impairment. Another important cause of visual impairment and blindness in the study was pterygium accounting for 23% and 19% of unilateral and bilateral visual impairment, 7% and 4% of unilateral and bilateral blindness respectively. The report showed that 87.5% of the blindness and 75.7% of the bilateral visual impairment were

avoidable. These largely agreed with the pattern and causes of blindness in other parts of sub-Saharan Africa.

Omotoye (2018) conducted a study on 'Prevalence and causes of visual impairment in Ekiti, Nigeria'. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The population of the study comprised of 1144 primary pupils and secondary students (504 males and 640 females) in Ilesa East Local Government Area of Ekiti State Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 220. A multi-stage random sampling method was employed in selecting the samples. The instruments administered for collecting the data were Checklist and questionnaire. The data obtained were analyzed using simple percent. The findings of the study indicated that a total of 97 (44.2%) of the school children were found to have visual impairment. These included blindness 43 (19.5%) and low vision 54 (24.5%).

2.8 Summary and Uniqueness of the Study

2.8.1 Summary of the Study

This chapter reviewed extensively several literatures on visual impairment, Braille literacy skill, typewriting skill, theoretical perspectives such as literacy acquisition theory, drill and practice theory as well as empirical studies. The concept of visual impairment was extensively reviewed in the sense that various scholarly literatures were used in explaining the concept of visual impairment. Various definitions of visual impairment from several scholars were reviewed. Similarly, the definitions of visual impairment have been divided into medical, educational and occupational as explained by the scholars. Also, scholarly write up was reviewed on characteristics of visual impairment. Classification of children with visual impairment as explained by scholars was also examined and reviewed in this chapter. Lastly, causes of visual impairment and refractive errors in children with visual impairment were critically examined and reviewed from literatures of various scholars.

In addition, the concept of Braille was extensively examined and reviewed in this chapter whereby different scholarly literature that explain the concept of Braille were used. Likewise, Braille writing devices such as slate and stylus, Perkins Brailier and electronic Braille embosser were examined and reviewed for this study. Also, the mechanics of reading Braille was extensively examined and reviewed as explained by scholar. Approaches of teaching Braille literacy skills were equally examined and reviewed in this chapter. Various scholars explained in detail the approaches of teaching Braille literacy skills. Too, Braille skills taught to children with visual impairment as identified by scholars were examined and reviewed in this chapter. Lastly, factors influencing Braille literacy skills as opined by scholars were examined and reviewed.

Furthermore, the concept of typewriting was examined and reviewed in this chapter in the sense that the literatures of various scholars were used in this chapter. Also, description of typewriters as explained by scholar was examined and reviewed in this chapter. Lastly, typewriting skills taught to children with visual impairment as identified by scholars were examined and reviewed.

Moreso, academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment was examined and reviewed in this chapter whereby several scholarly explanation on academic Performance were examined and reviewed in this chapter.

The theoretical framework of the study which consists of two theories: literacy acquisition theory as well as drill and practice theory were examined and reviewed for this study. The literacy acquisition theory was propounded in 1880-1961 and it is on the assumption that children could not learn to read or write until they reach a mental age of readiness. While, the drill and practice theory was propounded in 1874-1994 and it is on the assumption that systematic repetition, repetitious exercise and multiple rehearsals lead to mastering of skills.

Finally, twelve (12) empirical studies were also examined and reviewed in this chapter. Previous empirical studies at home and abroad related to this study were extensively examined and reviewed.

2.8.2 Uniqueness of the Study

As it has been seen in this chapter, several empirical studies on Braille literacy and touch typing skills were conducted. Some of those studies showed significant differences in the level of Braille and touch typing skills among male and female children with visual impairment. Other studies revealed significant difference or no difference between Braille skill and touch typing skill among children with visual impairment. Despite all these, no study has been conducted to find out the level of typewriting skill and Braille literacy skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment, no study has been carried out to find out gender difference in the level of typewriting skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment. Also, the available studies do not look at effect of Braille skill and typewriting skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment. Therefore, from the identified gaps of the previous studies, this study investigates the effects of Braille and typewriting skills on academic Performance of primary school pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School TundunMaliki, Kano state.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the methodology employed in collecting the data related to the study. The chapter contained the following areas: research design, population of the study, sample size, sampling technique, data collection instrument, validity and reliability of instrument, data collection procedure, data analysis procedure.

3.2 Research Design

The research design for this study was quasi-experimental which adopted pretest-posttest control group design. According to James and Macmillan (2006), this design involves two groups (experimental and control groups). The groups are not pre-tested. Also, one group was exposed to experimental treatment and other group does not exposed. After the intervention, both groups were post-tested and the post-test mean scores were compared to measure and determine the effect of the variables being studied.

3.3 Population and Sample of Study

3.3.1 Population of the Study

The target population of this study included all Primary School Pupils with Visual Impairment at Special Education School TudunMaliki, Kano State. The total number of pupils was fifty three (53) and thus, they were presented below in table:

Table 1: Distribution of population of the study based on class and gender (N = 53)

Class	Male	Female	Total
Primary 1	4	5	9
Primary 2	5	4	9
Primary 3	8	3	11
Primary 4	3	6	9
Primary 5	3	1	4
Primary 6	6	5	11
Grand Total	29	24	53

Source: Pupils enrolment records in Special Education School TudunMaliki, Kano State (2021).

3.3.2 Sample Size of the Study

The sample size for this study was twenty four (24) pupils with visual impairment drawn from primary 4, 5 and 6 which were middle basic education. Among the twenty four (24) samples, twelve (12) were males while, the remaining twelve (12) were females.

3.3.3 Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used in selecting the samples of this was purposive sampling technique. In purposive sampling technique, only those that meet the required purpose or attributes are selected (Bichi, 2003). Hence, all the pupils with visual impairment in class 4, 5, and 6 were selected to be the subjects of the study. This was because they possessed the characteristics which the researcher was looking for. That is the samples were in middle basic education (primary 4 – 6).

3.4 Data Collection Instruments

Two instruments were used to collect data for this study. The instruments included: Braille Writing Skill Test (BWST) and Typewriting Skill Test (TST), all were researcher's made. Hence, they were explained in details below:

3.4.1 Description of Braille Writing Skills Test (BWST)

It was constructed and designed by the researcher. The instrument was administered to primary 4,5,6 pupils with visual impairment in order to assess and measure their Braille writing skills. The instrument also contained two sections: A & B. Section A explored the bio-data of a pupil like name, gender, age, type of vision loss. While section B contained 5 questions to measure Braille writing proficiency of a pupil.

3.4.2 Description of Typewriting Skills Test (TST)

It was constructed and designed by the researcher. The instrument was administered to primary 4,5,6 pupils with visual impairment in order to assess and measure their typewriting skills. The instrument also contained two sections: A & B. section A explored the bio-data of a pupils like name, gender, age, type of vision loss. While section B contained 5 questions to measure typewriting proficiency of a pupil.

3.5 Validation of Instruments

3.5.1 Validity of Braille Writing Skills Test(BWST)

This instrument was subjected to content validity. According to Gay, Airasian and Mills (2009), a content validity is a type of validity which refers to the degree to which a test include or present all the contents of particular construct to measure what it is intended to measure. Hence, the Braille Writing Skills Test (BWST) was constructed and designed in line with the curriculum contents of Braille for primary school pupils with visual impairment. Also, to re-validate this instrument (BWST), it was submitted to expert in Braille literacy which include the supervisor of this study for corrections and modifications before the final draft was produced.

3.5.2 Reliability of Braille Writing Skills Test (BWST)

To determine the reliability coefficient of this instrument, the researcher employed test-retest technique of finding out reliability coefficient. According to Charles (2005), to find out the reliability coefficient using test-retest technique, the researcher administered the test to the same group of sample (pupils) on two separate occasions within two weeks interval. Therefore, this instrument (BWST) was administered twice with an interval of

two weeks to 10 pupils with visual impairment in School for the Blind Katsina. The data collected from the pilot testing was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and obtained a reliability index of 0.82 (high) which is suitable and statistically reliable for this study.

3.5.3 Validity Typewriting Skills Test (TST)

This instrument was subjected to content validity. This instrument (Typewriting Skills Test) was constructed based on the curriculum contents of Typewriting Skills for primary school pupils with visual impairment. Moreso, the instrument was submitted to expert which include the supervisor of this study for useful corrections and modifications before the final copy was produced.

3.5.4 Reliability of Typewriting Skills Test (TST)

To ensure the reliability coefficient index of this instrument, the researcher followed test-retest technique. The researcher applied it two times to a pilot sample of (10) pupils with visual impairment in School for the Blind Katsina. who were excluded from the study with two weeks interval between the first test and the second test. The reliability (high) index of this instrument was calculated using correlation coefficient and found to be 0.79. Hence, this is appropriate for conducting this study.

3.6 Data Collection Procedure

Firstly, the researcher in accompany with the research assistant visited Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano and submitted an introductory letter to the Principal of the School to seek approval and cooperation in conducting the research in the school. After the approval, the researcher went back to the school for the second time and met with primary 4,5 and 6 pupils with visual impairment. The researcher interacted with them for one day.

The procedure for data collection involved the interventions on Braille writing skills and Typewriting skills. Thus, the participants (samples) of the study were divided into two groups: experimental and control groups. Each group contained twelve (12) pupils based on gender balance. The experimental group was given intervention on Braille writing skills and typewriting skills. The interventions lasted for 8 weeks. The lessons of the intervention of on Braille writing skills and Typewriting skills were conducted for 30 minutes respectively on Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday. Hence, the intervention schedule was as follows:

Table 2: Intervention Schedule

Week 1	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Dot position in the Braille cell. ii- Fingering position on the Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (a-j) ii- Roman one: upper keys (Q – P)
Day 3	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (k-t). ii-Roman two: home keys (A – semi colon).
Day 4	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (u-z). ii-Roman three: lower keys (Y – Hyphen).
Week 2	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (b,c,d,e,f,g). ii- Insertion of paper skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (h,j,k,l,m,n). ii- Shift key and shift lock skill in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (p,q,r,s,t,u). ii- Tabulator skill in Typewriter.

Day 4	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (v,w,x,y,z). ii- Carriage release lever skill in Typewriter.
Week 3	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Special wordsigns (and, for). ii- Carriage return lever skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Special wordsigns (of, the, with). ii- Platen skill in Typewriter
Day 3	i- Special signs as upper groupsigns (and, for). ii- Platen knobs skill in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Special signs as upper groupsigns (of, the, with). ii- Platen ball skill in Typewriter
Week 4	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Upper groupsigns (ch, gh). ii- Paper grips skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	ii- Upper groupsigns (sh, th, wh). ii- Paper guide skill in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- ch, gh, sh, th, wh, as wordsigns in Braille ii- Paper release lever skill in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Upper groupsigns (ed, er, ou, ow). ii- Feed rollers skill in Typewriter.
Week 5	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Upper groupsigns (st, ar, ing). ii- Line space regulator skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	I- Lower groupsigns at the beginning of a word or Braille line (be, con, dis). ii- Margin stop skill in Typewriter.

Day 3	i- Lower groupsigns in the middle of a word (ea, bb,). ii- Margin release key skill in Typewriter.
Day4	i- Lower groupsigns in the middle of a word (cc, ff, gg). ii- Back space key skill in Typewriter.
Week 6	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Lower groupsigns in any part of word (en, in). ii- Removal of paper skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Lower groupsigns that must be spaced from all other signs (be, were, his, was). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 3	i- Lower groupsigns that must be spaced from all other words but may in some cases be in contact with punctuation signs (enough, in). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 4	i- Shorforms in Braille (those beginning with "a"). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Week 7	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Shorforms in Braille (those beginning with "be"). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 2	i- Punctuation signs in Braille. ii- Punctuation mark identification in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- Cardinal numbers in Braille ii- Identification of numbers in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Ordinal numbers in Braille. ii- Identification of numbers in Typewriter (continue)

Week 8	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	Revision
Day 2	Revision
Day 3	Assessment Tests on Braille writing skills.
Day 4	Assessment Tests on Typewriting Skills.

In addition, lesson plan was written for each lesson on Braille writing skills and Typewriting skills. The intervention was conducted by the researcher and the research assistant during the normal school hours and lesson periods. After 8 weeks intervention, assessment test on Braille writing skills and Typewriting skills were conducted. The difference between the mean scores of both Braille writing skills and Typewriting skills was subjected to statistical analysis.

3.7 Data Analysis Procedure

The data were statistically analyzed using mean and standard deviation, and t-test for related and unrelated samples. The formula for mean, standard deviation and t-test are presented below:

Mean: $\bar{x} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$

Standard deviation: $S = \frac{\sqrt{\sum(x-x)^2}}{N}$

t-test for related sample:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\frac{\sqrt{\sum(x-\bar{x})^2 + \sum(y-\bar{y})^2}}{nx+ny-2}} \left(\frac{1}{nx} + \frac{1}{ny} \right)$$

t-test for unrelated sample:

$$t = \frac{\bar{D}}{\frac{\sqrt{\sum D^2 - (\sum D)^2}}{N}} \frac{1}{N(N-1)}$$

**CHAPTER FOUR
PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA**

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explained the presentation and analysis of data. The obtained data were analyzed and presented in tabular form. Therefore, this chapter contained the following areas: data analysis, summary of findings, and discussion on findings.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Hypothesis One: There is no significant mean effect of Braille writing skill on academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment.

Table 3: Summary of t-Test Post-test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups in Braille Writing Skill (N = 24)

Group	Σn	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-criti.	df	Level of Significance	Decision
Experimental group	12	67.90	11.50	6.53	1.71	22	0.05	H ₀₁ Rejected
Control group	12	34.30	7.20					

The table above showed the calculated t-value of 6.53 and the critical t-value of 1.71 with 22 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significances. From the table, it was observed that the calculated t-value 6.53 was greater than the critical t-value 1.71. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant effect of Braille writing skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two: There is no significant mean effect of typewriting skill on academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment.

Table 4: Summary of t-Test Post-test Scores of Experimental and Control Groups in Typewriting Skill (N = 24)

Group	Σn	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-criti.	df	Level of Significance	Decision
Experimental group	12	64.50	10.70	11.12	1.71	22	0.05	H ₀₂ Rejected
Control Group	12	26.70	4.10					

The table above revealed the calculated t-value of 11.12 and the critical t-value of 1.71 with 22 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. From the table, the calculated t-value 11.10 was found to be greater than the critical t-value 1.71. Hence, with this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant effect of typewriting skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three: There is no significant mean difference between Braille writing and typewriting skills on academic Performance of pupils with visual impairment.

Table 5: Summary of t –Test Post-test Scores of Braille and Typewriting Skill (N = 24)

Skill	Σn	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-criti.	df	Level of Significance	Decision
Braille writing skill	12	67.9	11.50	4.93	1.796	22	0.05	H ₀₃ Rejected
Typewriting skill	12	26.7	4.10					

The table above shows the calculated t-value of 4.93 and the critical value of 1.796 with 22 degree of freedom at 0.05 level of significance. From the table, it was observed that the calculated t-value 4.93 is greater than the critical t-value 1.796. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected in favour of alternate hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant difference between the effect of Braille writing skill and the effect of typewriting skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment. Therefore, the Braille writing skill is better than typewriter skill in effect on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment.

4.2.4 Hypothesis Four: There is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skill mean scores of pupils with visual impairment.

Table 6: Summary of t-Test on Gender Difference in Braille Writing Skills (N = 12).

Gender	Σn	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-criti.	df	Level of Significance	Decision
Males	6	72.3	11.60	1.211	1.813	10	0.05	H ₀₄ Accepted
Females	6	63.5	9.60					

The table above indicated the calculated t-value of 1.21 and the critical t-value of 1.813 with degree of freedom of 10 at 0.05 level of significance. From the table, it was observed that the calculated t-value 1.211 was less than the critical t-value 1.813. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained, meaning that there is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skill of children with visual impairment.

4.2.5 Hypothesis Five: There is no significant gender difference in typewriting skill mean scores of pupils with visual impairment.

Table 7: Summary of t-Test on Gender Difference in Typewriting Skill (N = 12)

Gender	Σn	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	t-criti.	df	Level of Significance	Decision
Males	6	66.70	10.10	0.60	1.81	10	0.05	H ₀₅ Accepted
Females	6	62.30	10.90					

The table above showed the calculated t-value of 0.602 and the critical t-value of 1.813 with degree of freedom of 10 at 0.05 level of significance. From the table, the calculated t-value 0.60 was found to be less than the critical t-value 1.813. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained. This means that there is no significant gender difference in typewriting skills of children with visual impairment.

4.3 Summary of Findings

The following are the major summary of findings discovered by the researcher in this study:

1. There is a significant effect of Braille writing skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment.

2. There is a significant effect of typewriting skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment.
3. There is a significant difference between the effect of Braille writing skills and the effect of typewriting skill.
4. There is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skills of children with visual impairment.
5. There is no significant gender difference in typewriting skills of children with visual impairment.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One of this study revealed that There is a significant effect of Braille writing skills on academic Performance of children with visual impairment in favour of the experimental group (obtained t-value $6.53 > 1.711$ critical t-value). This finding agrees with the finding of Bandam (2018) who formulated hypothesis that there is no significant effect of Braille literacy skills on academic performance of pupils with visual impairment and tested the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of alternate hypothesis, meaning that, there is statistically significant effect of Braille literacy skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $2.12 > 1.14$ critical value). Also, this finding is supported by Daniela's finding (2015) which indicated that there was significant difference in Braille skills between the two groups of children with visual impairment: those exposed to Braille skills intervention and those who have not exposed (obtained t-value $2.43 > 1.362$ critical value). Hence, Braille skills had effect on academic performance of children with visual impairment.

Hypothesis Two of this study showed that There is a significant effect of typewriting skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment (obtained t-

value $11.112 > 1.711$ critical t-value). This finding coincides with the finding of Naqvi and Hashim (2011) who formulated a null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of children who were exposed to skill of touch typing (experimental group) and those were not (control group), and the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of alternate hypothesis (obtained t-value $2.048 > 0.335$ critical value). This means that the skill of touch typing had positive effect on academic performance of children with visual impairment. Likewise, this finding is in consonance with the finding of Tesselhor (2010) which indicated that there was statistically significant difference between the mean scores of experimental group and the mean scores of control group in touch typing skills obtained t-value $2.17 > 1.023$ critical t-value and thus, concluded that there is a significant effect of touch typing skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment.

Hypothesis Three of this study indicated that there is significant difference between Braille writing skill and typewriting skill on academic Performance of children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $4.911 >$ critical value). This finding is in agreement with the finding of Pauni (2014) who formulated the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of both Braille writing skill and the skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment, tested the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significant; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected in favour of alternate hypothesis, meaning that there is significant difference between the mean scores of both Braille writing skill and the skill of touch typing among children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $2.74 > 1.645$) critical value). However, the finding of this study contradicts with the finding of Russel (2011) who found that, there was no significant difference between Braille skill and touch typing skills among elementary school children with visual impairment (calculated t-value $0.32 < 1.421$ critical value).

Hypothesis Four of this study revealed that there is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skills of children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $1.21 < 1.813$ critical t-value). This finding is in line with the finding of Zainora (2011) who formulated hypothesis that there is no significant difference in Braille writing skill between male and female children with visual impairment, and the author tested the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted against alternate hypothesis (obtained t-value $0.25 < 2.028$ critical value). Also, the finding of this study corroborates with the finding of Okereke (2003) which indicated that there was no statistically significance difference between the mean scores of male and female children with visual impairment in the level of Braille reading and writing skills (obtained t-value $1.346 < 2.413$ critical value). However, the finding of this study is in contrary with the finding of Martos (2006) who found that there was significant statistical difference in Braille writing skills between boys and girls with visual impairment (obtained t-value $3.16 > 2.421$ critical t-value).

Hypothesis Five of this study indicated that, there is no significant gender difference in typewriting skills of children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $0.602 < 1.813$ critical t-value). This finding disagreed with the finding of Naqvi and Hashim (2011) who formulated a null hypothesis that there is no significant gender differences in touch typing skill among children with visual impairment, and they tested the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis was retained against the alternate hypothesis (obtained t-value $2.145 < 2.942$ critical value). Similarly, The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Goldberg (2016) which showed that there was no statistically significant difference in the level of typewriting skills between male and female children with visual impairment (obtained t-value $0.24 < 2.031$ critical t-value).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter explained the following areas: summary, conclusion, recommendations from the study and recommendations for further studies.

5.2 Summary

Chapter One, was the introduction which contained areas like the background to the study which traced the development of the conditions and factors necessitated the study as explained by various scholars. Statement of the problem which led to the study was stated. Also, in chapter one, five objectives of the study were outlined and five null hypotheses were formulated based on the research objectives of the study. The significance of the study was explained as well as scope and delimitation of the study. Finally, operational definitions of the key terms were mentioned.

Chapter Two, discussed the review of related literature whereby some scholarly writes up were examined and reviewed on the concept of visual impairment as explained by different scholars. Other areas that were examined and reviewed include: characteristics of children with visual impairment, classification of children with visual impairment, causes of visual impairment, refractive errors in children with visual impairment, concept of Braille as explained by severe scholars, mechanics of reading Braille, approaches of teaching Braille literacy skills, Braille skill taught to children with visual impairment, factors influencing Braille literacy skills, concept of typewriting skill as explained by various scholars, description of typewriters, typewriting skills taught to children with visual impairment, academic Performance of children with visual impairment, theoretical framework which comprised of literacy acquisition theory and drill and practice theory were all examined and reviewed. In addition, various empirical studies. Finally, summary and uniqueness of the study was discussed.

Chapter Three discussed the methodology used in collecting data of the study, areas in the chapter include: the research design which was quasi-experimental, population of the study which comprised of primary school pupils with visual impairment, sample size of the study was pupils in middle basic education, sampling technique which was a purposive, data collection instruments which were Braille Writing Skills Test (BWST) and Typewriting Skill Test (TST), validation of data collection instruments, data collection procedure which was through intervention, and finally data analysis procedure which employed T-test, mean and standard deviation as well as simple percentage statistical method of data analysis.

Chapter Four discussed the presentation and analysis of data. The data obtained were presented in tabular form and analyzed.

5.3 Conclusion

This study showed that the effect of typewriting skills was positive on academic performance of children with visual impairment when properly exposed to typewriter skills. Similarly, there was a great significant effect of Braille writing skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment. There was a great significant effect of typewriting skills on academic performance of children with visual impairment. There is no significant gender difference in Braille writing skills of children with visual impairment. There was no significant gender difference in typewriting skills of children with visual impairment.

5.4 Recommendations

5.4.1 Recommendations from the Study

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Pupils with visual impairment should be motivated to constantly practice Braille Writing Skills in order to improve their academic performance.
2. Pupils with visual impairment should be motivated to constantly practice typewriting skills in order to improve their academic performance.
3. Braille Writing Skills should be taught at early stage i.e primary 1, 2 and 3 while typewriting skills should be taught simultaneously with Braille writing skills at middle basic education i.e primary 4, 5 and 6 to pupils with visual impairment.
4. There should be constant and consistent instruction in Braille Writing Skills for both male and female pupils with visual impairment.
5. There should be constant and consistent instruction in typewriting skills for both male and female pupils with visual impairment.

5.4.2 Recommendations for Further Studies

1. A study should be conducted on effectiveness of Braille Skills and Typewriting Skills on academic performance of Pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School TudunMaliki, Kano State.
2. A study should be conducted on challenges faced by pupils with visual impairment in learning English Braille at Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.
3. A study should be conducted on problems of teaching typewriting skills to pupils with visual impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.

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APPENDIX A

BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO

FACULTY OF EDUCATION

DEPARTMENT OF SPECIAL EDUCATION

PMB 3011, Kano Nigeria

Vice-Chancellor: Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas B.Sc., Ed, M.Sc. Ed, (BUK) PhD. (ABU) FMAN
Head of Department: Dr. Ya'u Musa Dantata PhD (BUK), M.Ed, B.Ed (Jos), NCE (OYO)

Our Ref: BUK/DSE/077

Your Ref:

Date: 25th August, 2021

The Principal,
Special Education School, Tudun Maliki,
Kumbotso Local Government Area,
Kano State.

Dear Sir,

INTRODUCTORY LETTER

This is to introduce our student SAIFULLAHI MUKHTAR SADIQ with Registration Number SPS/18/MSE/00030 to you. He is M.Ed candidate conducting research on: *Effect of Braille Skills and Typewriting Skills on Academic Achievement of Primary School Pupils With Visual Impairment in Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano State.* Your school was selected for the study and all information will be treated confidentially, as it can only be used for educational purpose.

Please kindly accept and render him any assistance that he may require. —

Thanks for your usual cooperation.

Yours faithfully,

Dr. Atwat Inuwa Bello
PG Level Coordinator

APPENDIX B1

BRAILLE WRITING SKILL TEST (BWST) FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT

Introduction

This is a test designed and constructed by the research. It is used to assess and measure the Braille Writing Skill of primary school pupils with visual impairment.

Section A: Bio-Data of pupil

Name: _____

Gender: _____

Age: _____

Type of vision loss: _____

Class: _____

School: _____

Date: _____

Section B: Braille Writing Items

Instruction: Below are letters, words and sentences which a pupil will write in Braille.

1. Write the following letters of alphabet in Braille

a	k	u
b	i	v
c	m	w
d	n	x
e	o	y
f	p	z
g	q	
h	r	
i	s	
j	t	

(26 marks)

2. What do the following letters represent in Braille:

B J Q V

E L S X

G N U Z

(24 marks)

3. Write the sign representing the following words in Braille:

And

For

Of

The

With

(10 marks)

4. Write the following words in Braille using correct Braille contractions:

Land	School	Bed	For	Beat
Form	High	Writer	Getting	Rabbit
Profit	Dish	House	Belief	Access
Them	Bath	Brown	Control	Effect
Within Whole	Stress	Disgrace	Enjoy	

(26 marks)

5. Write the following sentences in Braille:

- i. He was a teacher before
- ii. Are you interested in the game?
- iii. She said, "they were given 25 naira and above".
- iv. My father travelled to England five days ago:
- v. I like to become a teacher; so I must study hard.
- vi. You do not have enough time!
- vii. 'His knowledge will benefit people'

(14 marks)

APPENDIX B2

TYPEWRITING SKILL TEST (TST) FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT

Introduction

This is a test designed and constructed by the researcher. It is used to assess and measure the typewriting skill of primary school pupils with visual impairment.

Section A: Bio-data of pupil

Name: _____

Gender: _____

Age: _____

Type of vision loss: _____

Class: _____

School: _____

Date: _____

Section B: Typewriting Items

Instruction: Below are letters, words and sentences which a pupil will write by using typewriter.

1. Write the following letters of alphabet by using Typewriter

a	k	u
b	i	v
c	m	w
d	n	x
e	o	y
f	p	z

5. Write the following sentences by using typewriter:

1. He was a teacher before,
2. Are you interested in the game?
3. She said, “they were given 25 naira and above”.
4. My father travelled to England five days ago:
5. I like to become a teacher; so I must study hard.
6. You do not have enough time!

‘His knowledge will benefit people’

(14 marks)

APPENDIX C
INTERVENTION SCHEDULE ON BRAILL WRITING SKILL AND
TYPEWRITING SKILL

Week 1	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Dot position in the Braille cell. ii- Fingering position on the Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (a-j) ii- Roman one: upper keys (Q – P)
Day 3	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (k-t). ii-Roman two: home keys (A – semi colon).
Day 4	i- Letters of alphabet in Braille (u-z). ii-Roman three: lower keys (Y – Hyphen).
Week 2	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (b,c,d,e,f,g). ii- Insertion of paper skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (h,j,k,l,m,n). ii- Shift key and shift lock skill in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (p,q,r,s,t,u). ii- Tabulator skill in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Letters as simple upper wordsigns in Braille (v,w,x,y,z). ii- Carriage release lever skill in Typewriter.
Week 3	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Special wordsigns (and, for). ii- Carriage return lever skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	i- Special wordsigns (of, the, with). ii- Platen skill in Typewriter

Day 3	i- Special signs as upper groupsigns (and, for). ii- Platen knobs skill in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Special signs as upper groupsigns (of, the, with). ii- Platen ball skill in Typewriter
Week 4	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Upper groupsigns (ch, gh). ii- Paper grips skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	ii- Upper groupsigns (sh, th, wh). ii- Paper guide skill in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- ch, gh, sh, th, wh, as wordsigns in Braille ii- Paper release lever skill in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Upper groupsigns (ed, er, ou, ow). ii- Feed rollers skill in Typewriter.
Week 5	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Upper groupsigns (st, ar, ing). ii- Line space regulator skill in Typewriter.
Day 2	I- Lower groupsigns at the beginning of a word or Braille line (be, con, dis). ii- Margin stop skill in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- Lower groupsigns in the middle of a word (ea, bb,). ii- Margin release key skill in Typewriter.
Day4	i- Lower groupsigns in the middle of a word (cc, ff, gg). ii- Back space key skill in Typewriter.
Week 6	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Lower groupsigns in any part of word (en, in). ii- Removal of paper skill in Typewriter.

Day 2	i- Lower groupsigns that must be spaced from all other signs(be, were, his, was). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 3	i- Lower groupsigns that must be spaced from all other words but may in some cases be in contact with punctuation signs (enough, in). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 4	i- Shorforms in Braille (those beginning with "a"). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Week 7	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	i- Shorforms in Braille (those beginning with "be"). ii- Typewriting drill and practice
Day 2	i- Punctuation signs in Braille. ii- Punctuation mark identification in Typewriter.
Day 3	i- Cardinal numbers in Braille ii- Identification of numbers in Typewriter.
Day 4	i- Ordinal numbers in Braille. ii- Identification of numbers in Typewriter (continue)
Week 8	Topics: Braille skills and Typewriting skills
Day 1	Revision
Day 2	Revision
Day 3	Assessment Tests on Braille writing skills.
Day 4	Assessment Tests on Typewriting Skills.

APPENDIX D1
LESSON PLAN ON BRAILLE WRITING SKILLS

Name of School:	Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano state
Section:	Visually Impaired Section
Date:	6 th September, 2021
Subject:	Braille Skills
Topic:	Letters of Alphabet in Braille (a-j)
Time:	11:00 – 11:30am
Duration:	30minutes
Class:	Primary 4 – 6
Gender:	Mixed (Males & Females)
Average Age of Pupils:	10years
Ratio of Pupils:	12males: 12females
Reference Book:	Unified English Braille Primer (2009 Edition)
Instructional Materials:	Slate and Stylus
Entry Behaviour:	The pupils were taught the dot position in Braille cell.
Behavioural Objectives:	At the end of this lesson, the pupils should be able to: <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Write letter a – j in Braille2. Identify letter a – j given in Braille format
Specific Objectives:	At the end of this lesson, 70% of the pupils should be able to practice writing the Braille of letter a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i,

Introduction:	The teacher introduces the lesson by asking the pupils questions, e.g How many Braille dots position?
Presentation:	The teacher presents the lesson through the following steps:
Step 1:	The teacher describes the dots position of letter a to j for
Step 2:	The teacher guides the pupils to write the letter a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j in Braille
Step 3:	The pupils are allowed to identify letter a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i, and j, in Braille.
Evaluation:	The teacher evaluates the lesson based on the following questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Write letter a – j in Braille 2. Identify a – j given in Braille format
Conclusion:	The teacher concludes the lesson by going round to give help where necessary. Likewise, the teacher allows the pupils to ask questions concerning the lesson.
Remark:	The lesson have been conducted successfully

APPENDIX D2
LESSON PLAN ON TYPEWRITING SKILLS

Name of School:	Special Education School Tudun Maliki, Kano state
Section:	visually Impaired Section
Date:	6 th September, 2021
Subject:	Typewriting Skills
Topic:	Roman One: Upper Keys (Q – P)
Time:	11 - 30am – 12:00pm
Duration:	30 minutes
Class:	Primary 4 – 6
Gender:	Mixed (Males & Females)
Average Age of Pupils:	10 years
Ratio of Pupils:	12 males: 12 females
Reference Book:	Typewriting skill guide (Handbook for the Beginners)
Instructional Materials:	Portable Typewriters
Previous Knowledge:	The pupils were taught the fingering position on Typewriter
Behavioural Objectives:	At the end of this lesson, the pupils should be able to: 1. Identify the upper keys of typewriter (Q – P) 2. Use the upper keys of typewriter (Q – P)
Specific Objectives:	At the end of this lesson, 65% of the pupils should be able to practice writing by using the upper keys of typewriter.

Introduction:	The teacher introduces the lesson by asking the pupils questions, e.g 1. How many key parts in typewriter.
Presentation:	The teacher presents the lesson by the following steps:
Step 1:	The teacher describes the upper keys (Q – P) of typewriter for the pupils
Step 2:	The teacher guides the pupils to use the upper keys of the typewriter.
Step 3:	The pupils are allowed by the teacher to practice writing with upper keys of the typewriter
Evaluation:	The teacher evaluates the lesson based on the following questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identify the upper keys of typewriter (Q – P). 2. Use the upper keys of typewriter in writing
Conclusion:	The teacher concludes the lesson by going round to give help where necessary. Likewise, the teacher allows the pupils to ask questions concerning the lesson.
Remark:	The lesson has been conducted successfully.

APPENDIX E1
COMPUTATION OF MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF SCORES ON
BRAILLE WRITING SKILLS

Experimental Group (N = 12)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
60	3600
65	4225
55	3025
80	6400
51	2601
70	4900
85	7225
72	5184
60	3600
56	3136
86	7396
75	5625
$\Sigma X = 815$	$\Sigma X^2 = 56914$

Mean: $\bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{815}{12} = 67.9$

Variance: $S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{56914}{12} - 67.9^2$
 $= 4742.83 - 4610.41$
 $= 132.42$

Standard deviation: $S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$
 $= \sqrt{132.42}$
 $= 11.50$

Experimental Group: Females (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
60	3600
65	4225
55	3025
80	6400
51	2601
70	4900
$\Sigma X = 381$	$\Sigma X^2 = 24751$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{381}{12} = 63.5$$

$$\text{Variance: } S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2$$

$$= \frac{24751}{6} - 63.5^2$$

$$= 4125.16 - 4032.25$$

$$= 92.91$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation: } S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$$

$$= \sqrt{92.91}$$

$$= 9.63$$

Experimental Group: Males (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
85	7225
72	5184
75	5625
60	3600
56	3136
86	7396
$\Sigma X = 434$	$\Sigma X^2 = 32166$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{434}{6} = 72.3$$

$$\text{Variance: } S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{32166}{6} - 72.3^2$$

$$= 5361 - 5227.29$$

$$= 133.71$$

$$\text{Standard deviation: } S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$$

$$= \sqrt{133.71}$$

$$= 11.56$$

Control Group (N = 12)

Scores X	Scores squared X²
35	1225
28	784
40	1600
35	1225
38	1444
31	961
32	1024
45	2025
48	2304
30	900
20	400
29	841
$\Sigma X = 411$	$\Sigma X^2 = 14733$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{411}{12} = 34.3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{14733}{12} - 34.3^2 \\ &= 1227.75 - 1176.49 \\ &= 51.26 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{51.26} \\ &= 7.2 \end{aligned}$$

Control Group: Females (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X²
32	1024
45	2025
48	2305
30	900
20	400
29	841
$\Sigma X = 204$	$\Sigma X^2 = 7495$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{204}{6} = 34$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{7495}{6} - 34^2 \\ &= 1249.16 - 1156 \\ &= 93.16 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{93.16} \\ &= 9.65 \end{aligned}$$

Control Group: Male

Scores X	Scores squared X²
35	1225
28	784
40	1600
35	1225
38	1444
31	961
$\Sigma X = 207$	$\Sigma X^2 = 7239$

Mean: $\bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = 34.5$

Variance: $S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{7239}{6} - 34.5^2$
 $= 1206.5 - 1190.25$
 $= 16.25$

Standard deviation: $S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$
 $= \sqrt{16.25}$
 $= 4.03$

APPENDIX E2
COMPUTATION OF MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF SCORES ON
TYPEWRITING SKILLS

Experimental Group (N = 12)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
84	7056
54	2916
66	4356
57	3249
52	2704
61	3721
83	6889
62	3844
78	6084
61	3721
54	2916
62	3844
$\Sigma X = 774$	$\Sigma X^2 = 51300$

Mean: $\bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{774}{12} = 64.5$

Variance: $S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{51300}{12} - 64.5^2$
 $= 4275 - 4160.25$
 $= 114.75$

Standard deviation: $S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$
 $= \sqrt{114.75}$
 $= 10.71$

Experimental Group: Females (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
84	7056
54	2916
66	4356
57	3249
52	2704
61	3721
$\Sigma X = 374$	$\Sigma X^2 = 24002$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{374}{6} = 62.3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{24002}{6} - 62.3^2 \\ &= 4000.33 - 3881.29 \\ &= 119.04 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{119.04} \\ &= 10.91 \end{aligned}$$

Experimental Group: Males (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
83	6889
62	3844
62	3844
78	6084
61	3721
54	2916
$\Sigma X = 400$	$\Sigma X^2 = 27298$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{400}{6} = 66.7$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{27298}{6} - 66.7^2 \\ &= 4549.66 - 4448.89 \\ &= 100.77 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{100.77} \\ &= 10.03 \end{aligned}$$

Control Group (N = 12)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
32	1024
28	784
22	484
30	900
25	625
20	400
29	841
34	1156
21	441
30	900
23	529
26	676
$\Sigma X = 320$	$\Sigma X^2 = 8760$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{320}{12} = 26.7$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{8760}{12} - 26.7^2 \\ &= 730 - 712.89 \\ &= 17.11 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{17.11} \\ &= 4.13 \end{aligned}$$

Control Group: Females (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
32	1024
28	784
22	484
30	900
25	625
20	400
$\Sigma X = 157$	$\Sigma X^2 = 4217$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{157}{6} = 26.2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Variance: } S^2 &= \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{4217}{6} - 26.2^2 \\ &= 702.83 - 686.44 \\ &= 16.39 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Standard deviation: } S &= \sqrt{\text{variance}} \\ &= \sqrt{16.39} \\ &= 4.04 \end{aligned}$$

Control Group: Males (N = 6)

Scores X	Scores squared X ²
29	841
34	1156
21	441
36	900
23	529
26	676
$\Sigma X = 163$	$\Sigma X^2 = 4543$

Mean: $\bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{N} = \frac{163}{6} = 27.2$

Variance: $S^2 = \frac{\Sigma X^2}{N} - \bar{x}^2 = \frac{4543}{6} - 27.2^2$
 $= 757.17 - 739.84$
 $= 17.32$

Standard deviation: $S = \sqrt{\text{variance}}$
 $= \sqrt{17.32}$
 $= 4.16$

APPENDIX E3
COMPUTATION OF T-TEST FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BETWEEN
EXPERIMENTAL GROUP AND CONTROL GROUP ON SCORES OF BRAILLE
WRITING SKILLS

Pupils	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Experimental Group Scores	60	65	55	80	51	70	85	72	60	56	86	75
Control Group Scores	35	28	40	35	38	31	32	45	48	30	20	29

Experimental Group Scores (x) (N =12)	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	Control Group Scores (y) (N =12)	$y - \bar{y}$	$(y - \bar{y})^2$
60	-2.4	5.76	35	0.7	0.49
65	2.6	6.76	28	-6.3	39.69
55	-7.4	54.76	40	5.7	32.49
80	17.6	309.76	35	0.7	0.49
51	-11.4	129.96	38	3.7	13.69
70	7.6	57.76	31	-3.3	10.89
85	22.6	510.76	32	-2.3	5.29
72	9.6	92.16	45	10.7	114.49
60	-2.4	5.76	48	13.7	187.69
56	-6.4	40.96	30	-4.3	18.49
86	23.6	556.95	20	-14.3	204.49
75	12.6	158.76	29	-5.3	28.09
$\Sigma x = 815$		$\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2 =$ 1930.11	$\Sigma y = 411$		$\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2 =$ 656.28

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{n} = \frac{815}{12} = 67.9$$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{y} = \frac{\Sigma y}{n} = \frac{411}{12} = 34.3$$

Therefore:

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2}{nx} + \frac{\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2}{ny}}} \left(\frac{1}{nx} + \frac{1}{ny} \right)$$

$$t = \frac{67.9 - 34.3}{\sqrt{\frac{1930.11}{12} + \frac{656.28}{12}}} \left(\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{12} \right)$$

$$t = \frac{28.1}{\sqrt{2586.39}} (0.08 + 0.08)$$

$$t = \frac{28.1}{\sqrt{117.56}} \quad (0.16)$$

$$t = \frac{28.1}{\sqrt{117.56 \times 0.16}}$$

$$t = \frac{28.1}{\sqrt{18.8}}$$

$$t = \frac{28.1}{4.3}$$

$$t = 6.534 \text{ (t - calculated value)}$$

$$df = n_x + n_y - 2$$

$$= 12 + 12 - 2$$

$$= 22$$

$$t - \text{critical value} = 1.711$$

$$\text{level of significance} = 0.05$$

APPENDIX E4
COMPUTATION OF T-TEST FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BETWEEN
MALE'S SCORES AND FEMALE'S SCORES OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP ON
BRILLE WRITING SKILLS

Pupils	1	2	3	4	5	6
Males Scores	85	72	75	60	56	86
Females Scores	60	65	55	80	51	70

Experimental Group Scores (x) (N=6)	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	Control Group Scores (y) (N=6)	$y - \bar{y}$	$(y - \bar{y})^2$
85	12.7	161.29	60	-3.5	12.25
72	-0.3	0.09	65	1.5	2.25
75	2.7	7.29	55	-8.5	72.25
60	-12.3	151.29	80	16.5	272.25
56	-16.3	265.69	51	-12.5	156.25
86	13.7	187.69	70	6.5	42.25
$\Sigma x = 434$		$\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2 =$ 773.34	$\Sigma y = 381$		$\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2 =$ 557.5

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{n} = \frac{434}{6} = 72.3$$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{y} = \frac{\Sigma y}{n} = \frac{381}{6} = 63.5$$

Therefore:

$$t = \frac{\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2}{n} + \frac{\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2}{n}}}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{nx} + \frac{1}{ny}}}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{72.3 - 63.5}{\sqrt{\frac{773.34}{6} + \frac{557.5}{6}}}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}}}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{8.8}{\sqrt{1330.84}}}{\sqrt{0.02 + 0.02}}$$

8.8

$$t = \sqrt{133.084} \quad (0.4)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{8.8}{133.084 \times 0.4}}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{8.8}{53.2}}$$

$$t = \frac{8.8}{7.3}$$

$$t = 1.205 \text{ (t - calculated value)}$$

$$df = n_x + n_y - 2$$

$$= 6 + 6 - 2$$

$$= 10$$

$$t - \text{critical value} = 1.813$$

$$\text{Level of significance} = 0.05$$

APPENDIX E5
COMPUTATION OF T-TEST FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BETWEEN
EXPERIMENTAL GROUP AND CONTROL GROUP ON SCORES OF
TYPEWRITING SKILLS

Pupils	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Experimental Group Scores	84	54	66	57	52	61	83	62	78	61	54	62
Control Group Scores	32	28	22	30	25	20	29	34	21	30	23	26

Experimental Group Scores (x) (N=12)	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	Control Group Scores (y) (N=12)	$y - \bar{y}$	$(y - \bar{y})^2$
84	19.5	380.25	32	5.3	28.09
54	-10.5	110.25	28	1.3	1.69
66	1.5	2.25	22	-4.7	22.09
57	-7.5	56.25	30	3.3	10.89
52	-12.5	156.25	25	-1.7	2.89
61	-3.5	12.25	20	-6.7	44.89
83	18.5	342.25	29	2.3	5.29
62	-2.5	6.25	34	7.3	53.29
78	13.5	182.25	21	-5.7	32.49
61	-3.5	12.25	30	3.3	10.89
54	-10.5	110.25	23	-3.7	13.69
62	-2.5	6.25	26	-0.7	0.49
$\Sigma x = 774$		$\Sigma(x-x)^2 = 1377$	$\Sigma y = 320$		$\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2 = 226.68$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{n} = \frac{774}{12} = 64.5$$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{y} = \frac{\Sigma y}{n} = \frac{320}{12} = 26.7$$

Therefore:

$$t = \frac{\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(x-\bar{x})^2}{n} + \frac{\Sigma(y-\bar{y})^2}{n}}}}{\left[\frac{1}{nx} + \frac{1}{ny} \right]}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{64.5 - 26.7}{\sqrt{\frac{1377}{12} + \frac{226.68}{12}}}}{\left[\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{12} \right]}$$

$$t = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{37.8}{1603.68}}}{22} \quad (0.08 + 0.08)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{37.8}{72.89}} \quad (0.16)$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{37.8}{72.89 \times 0.16}}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{37.8}{11.7}}$$

$$t = \frac{37.8}{3.4}$$

$$t = 11.117 \text{ (t – calculated value)}$$

$$df = n_x + n_y - 2$$

$$= 12 + 12 - 2$$

$$= 22$$

$$t - \text{critical value} = 1.711$$

$$\text{Level of significance} = 0.05$$

APPENDIX E6
COMPUTATION OF T-TEST FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES BETWEEN
MALES SCORES AND FEMALES SCORES OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP ON
TYPEWRITING SKILLS

Pupils	1	2	3	4	5	6
Males Scores	83	62	62	78	61	54
Females Scores	84	54	66	57	52	61

Experimental Group Scores (x) (N =6)	$x - \bar{x}$	$(x - \bar{x})^2$	Control Group Scores (y) (N =6)	$y - \bar{y}$	$(y - \bar{y})^2$
83	16.3	265.69	84	21.7	470.89
62	-4.7	22.09	54	-8.3	68.89
62	-4.7	22.09	66	3.7	13.69
78	11.3	127.69	57	-5.3	28.09
61	-5.7	32.49	52	-10.3	106.09
54	-12.7	161.29	61	-1.3	1.69
$\Sigma x = 400$		$\Sigma(x - \bar{x})^2 =$ 631.34	$\Sigma y = 374$		$\Sigma(y - \bar{y})^2 =$ 689.34

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{x} = \frac{\Sigma X}{n} = \frac{400}{6} = 66.7$$

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{y} = \frac{\Sigma y}{n} = \frac{374}{6} = 62.3$$

Therefore:

$$t = \frac{\frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{\Sigma(x-\bar{x})^2}{nx} + \frac{\Sigma(y-\bar{y})^2}{ny}}}}{\frac{1}{nx} + \frac{1}{ny}}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{66.7 - 62.3}{\sqrt{\frac{631.34}{6} + \frac{689.34}{6}}}}{\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{4.4}{\sqrt{1320.68}}}{10} \quad (0.02 + 0.02)$$

$$t = \frac{4.4}{\sqrt{1320.68}} \quad (0.4)$$

$$t = \frac{4.4}{\sqrt{1320.68} \times 0.4}$$

$$t = \frac{4.4}{\sqrt{52.8}}$$

$$t = \frac{4.4}{7.3}$$

t = 0.602 (t – calculated value)

$$df = n x + ny - 2$$

$$= 6 + 6 - 2$$

$$= 10$$

t – critical value = 1.813

Level of significance = 0.05

APPENDIX E7
COMPUTATION OF T-TEST FOR DEPENDENT SAMPLES BETWEEN
SCORES ON BRAILLE WRITING SKILL AND SCORES ON TYPEWRITING
SKILL OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP

Pupils	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Braille Writing Skill Scores	60	65	55	80	51	70	85	72	60	56	86	75
Typewriting Skill Scores	84	54	66	57	52	61	83	62	78	61	54	62

Pupils	Braille writing skill scores	Typewriting skill scores	D	D ²
1	60	84	-25	625
2	65	54	11	121
3	55	66	-11	121
4	80	57	23	529
5	51	52	-1	1
6	70	61	9	81
7	85	83	2	4
8	72	62	10	100
9	60	78	-18	324
10	56	61	-5	25
11	86	54	32	1024
12	75	62	13	169
Σx = 12			Σ(x-\bar{x})² = 160	Σy = 3124

$$\text{Mean: } \bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{n} = \frac{160}{12} = 13.3$$

Therefore:

$$t = \frac{\frac{\bar{D}}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - (\sum D)^2}{N(N-1)}}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - (\sum D)^2}{N(N-1)}}}$$

$$t = \frac{\frac{13.3}{\sqrt{\frac{3124 - (160)^2}{12(12-1)}}}}{\sqrt{\frac{3124 - (160)^2}{12(12-1)}}}$$

$$t = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{13.3}{\frac{3124 - 25600}{12}}}}{12(11)}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{13.3}{\frac{3124 - 2133.3}{132}}}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{13.3}{\frac{990.7}{132}}}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{13.3}{7.5}}$$

$$t = \sqrt{\frac{13.3}{2.7}}$$

$$t = \frac{13.3}{2.7}$$

$$t = 4.925 \text{ (t - calculated value)}$$

$$df = N - 1$$

$$= 12 - 1$$

$$= 11$$

$$t - \text{critical value} = 1.796$$

$$\text{Level of significance} = 0.05$$